

Master's Thesis

The Role of Counter-Hegemonic Narratives in a Post- Extractivist Transformation— Case Study Research on the Ecuadorian Referendum for Banning Oil Exploitation in the ITT Block in the Yasuni National Park

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Abstract

This thesis explores the role of counter-hegemonic narratives in promoting post-extractivist transformations, focusing on the Ecuadorian Yasuni National Park referendum of August 2023, which aimed to ban oil extraction in the ITT block. This thesis examines how narratives can contribute to imagining and promoting societal change and investigates how they challenge extractivism and envision a just, equitable, and sustainable future.

Drawing on the methodological framework of case study research outlined by Yin (2017), this study analyses data from the Yasuni referendum campaign. Using a constructivist grounded theory approach, aided by elements of narrative inquiry, the research analyses expert interviews and other complementary sources.

It explores how counter-hegemonic narratives—through symbolisms, historical identity building, and collective action—challenge extractivism and co-create alternative futures. The results suggest that critical framings of the world contribute to societal transformation by triggering imagination, agency and hope, thereby empowering individuals to be active part of change. However, narratives of change face significant challenges, including structural barriers, the dominance of hegemonic ideologies, and narrative volatility. Despite these limitations, the Yasuni referendum serves as a positive example of collective resistance and signals a desire for a shift toward sustainable development models.

Ultimately, the thesis argues that while narratives alone cannot change the world, they are necessary to foster transformative processes by expanding the realm of what is possible, challenging visions of a single future, and problematizing current systems of extractivism.

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Abbreviation list

CDES	Centre for Economic and Social Rights
CONAIE	National Confederation of Indigenous Nationalities of Ecuador
CONFENIAE	Confederation of Indigenous Nationalities of the Ecuadorian Amazon
D	Document
E	Expert
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
IMF	International Monetary Fund
ITT	Ishpingo, Tambococha, Tiputini
NAWE	Waorani Nationality Ecuador
PC	Press conference
PR	Press release
PUAM	Amazon University Programme
REPAM	Pan-Amazonian Ecclesial Network
SIL	Summer Institute of Linguistics
TINA	There-Is-No-Alternative
UDAPT	Union of People Affected by Texaco
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
ZITT	Intangible Zone Tagaeri Taromenane

1 Introduction

In an era marked by increasing environmental degradation, social inequality, and the looming threat of climate change, the imperative for social-ecological transformation has never been more pressing (Acosta & Brand, 2018). It is currently possible to point out that every region in the world faces multiple crises or increased socio-environmental conflicts (Acosta & Brand, 2018; Svampa, 2012). This presence of multiple crises is attributable to global conditions such as climate change, the asymmetric distribution of productive roles on a global scale, or to situations at the national and regional level, such as territorial transformations, lack of environmental regulation, or political inaction (Lopez, 2020).

Many of these crises are built on models of extractivism (Acosta, 2013), where socio-ecological conflicts proliferate. Demonstrating the discrepancy between societies that depend on the (neo-) extractivist development models and those that have aspirations for sustainability and global justice. This discrepancy between extractivism and environmental and social justice highlights the need for a future societal transformation that includes structural change and questions underlying economic models (Acosta & Brand, 2018; Gudynas, 2011a; Wright, 2013). However, how to achieve it or how such transformation should look seems a complex riddle.

Acosta (2013, p.62) defines extractivism as *"those activities which remove large quantities of natural resources that are not processed (or processed only to a limited degree), especially for export,"* which also includes within the terminology a specific *"mode of accumulation and appropriation."* Scholars widely agree that extractivism extends beyond resource extraction, manifesting as a social phenomenon fraught with violence and territorial dispossession (Acosta, 2013; Gudynas, 2011a; Svampa, 2012). Oil extraction notably inflicts irreparable cultural, social, and environmental harm (Gudynas, 2019; León, 2017).

Intellectuals argue that extractivism can lead to resource curse phenomena, referring to the paradoxical situation where countries rich in natural resources often experience economic stagnation, political instability, and social inequality instead of prosperity and development (Acosta, 2013; Gilberthorpe & Rajak, 2017; Ross, 1999). Despite the substantial global evidence highlighting the tension between development and extraction, the belief that resource-rich countries can use extractive activities to accelerate development—often referred to as 'extractivism'—remains widely accepted (Svampa, 2012).

Latin America is emblematic of expanding extractivism, with the extraction frontier of oil and mining advancing enormously into the Amazon (Arsel et al., 2016b). Despite this continent's long and dark history of natural resource extraction for export, modern development paradigms have placed extractivism at its heart (Acosta, 2001; Galeano, 1971). This story of necessity, dependency, and perceived lack of alternatives has led to the so-called resource curse (Ross, 1999), commodities consensus (Svampa, 2015), and extractive imperative (Arsel et al., 2016b), perpetuating socio-ecological conflicts in Latin America. In this context, responses to social and environmental issues continue to be predominantly oriented towards economic growth driven by modern, anthropocentric, colonial, capitalist, and patriarchal conceptions and models of development, further accelerating ecological exploitation and leading to the collapse of local and global ecosystems (Svampa & Viale, 2021).

Ecuador provides an illustrative example of the imperative need for extraction and its impacts (Arsel et al., 2016a). The country possesses abundant natural resources, particularly oil and minerals, attracting multinational corporations eager to exploit these resources for economic gain (Acosta, 2001; Swallow, 2017). However, extractivism in Ecuador has resulted in significant social and environmental consequences. The exploitation of oil and minerals has caused, among others, deforestation, contamination of rivers and ecosystems, deterioration of health standards, and the displacement of Indigenous communities residing in resource-rich areas (Eugenio et al., 2024; León, 2017; Soliz Torres et al., 2023).

Perspectives on extractivism as an imperative necessity in Ecuador and its political and financial dependency on non-renewable resource extraction are nothing new. Ecuador was a past colony producing raw materials to be taken to Europe (Acosta, 2001). The colonial system was based on models of racialization with forced labour, slavery, and power. When the colonial period ended, it left traces of social division and the first debts that the country would have (Acosta, 2001). Since then, Ecuador has experienced the adverse effects of the "resource curse." Despite substantial oil revenues, the country has struggled with persistent social inequality, political instability, and a lack of economic diversification, impeding sustainable development (Larrea, 2024; León, 2017; Swallow, 2017).

Therefore, several scholars call for a post-extractivist transformation characterized by efforts to move away from the extractive model, which includes establishing independent governance, reclaiming cultural identity, and addressing the legacies of colonialism, such as those established in extractivism (Acosta,

2017; Acosta & Brand, 2018; Gudynas, 2011a; Svampa, 2012; Unceta, 2018). The country has also experienced a growing demand from the population for alternative modes of development. As part of a country where social and environmental movements are notable for their long-standing trajectory and the presence of vocal and influential groups that actively advocate for societal change (Mancilla & Martínez, 2014; Unceta, 2018). In 2008, a new constitution was written that established a plurinational state and the *Sumak Kawsay* or *Bien Vivir* as a central element, which also included the declaration of rights of nature and indigenous peoples (Asamblea Nacional, 2008).

An internationally known example of the desire for alternatives to conventional extractivism as the promotor of development is the Yasuni-ITT¹ initiative, which sought to leave oil reserves on the ground in exchange for economic aid from countries of the global North. This initiative was not carried out. However, social groups demanded that the oil be left in the ground for the intrinsic value of the area and not for monetary gain (Mancilla & Martínez, 2014). Although this request was not heeded, the YASunidos collective succeeded in getting the decision to exploit the ITT block of the Yasuni National Park put to a people's consultation, or referendum, in August 2023 (Brito, 2020; CNE, 2023a). The referendum, held over a decade after the proposal of the ITT initiative, yielded results favouring the conservation of the Yasuní (CNE, 2023b).

Yasuni's case once again crystallized that the state is interested in extracting its natural resources regardless of the social and environmental harm it causes. Ecuador had an important oil boom in the 70s, and since then, the need to exploit fossil resources has constantly been present in political decisions and discourses (Acosta, 2017; Larrea, 2024). However, this position has increasingly come under attack, driven not only by concerns about the negative socio-environmental impacts of extractivism (Acosta, 2017; León, 2017) but also by the recognition of its detrimental effects on climate, environment, and social aspects associated with fossil fuels (IPCC, 2022). Petroleum activities, for instance, have environmental impacts throughout their phases, from exploration and prospecting to operation and even in abandoned fields. These impacts include access roads, various types of drilling, pipeline networks, pumping installations, and disposal sites for water, sludge, and waste (Finer et al., 2009; Orszulik, 2007; E. Suárez et al., 2009). Moreover, there is abundant evidence of negative social impacts such as territorial invasion, deterioration in public health, human rights violations, and participation in corruption networks (Gudynas, 2011b; Mancilla & Martínez, 2014; Soliz Torres et al., 2023).

¹ The Yasuni-ITT Initiative was named after the Ishpingo-Tambococha-Tiputini (ITT) oil fields in block 43 within the Yasuni National Park

The notion that no alternative to extractivism exists has been produced and sustained by powerful institutions with apparent political interests, demonstrating a hegemonic nature (Brand & Wissen, 2012; Gramsci, 1992; Gudynas, 2011b). Consequently, counter-extractivist narratives face significant challenges when confronting robust, institutionalized, and widely disseminated hegemonic structures (Gudynas, 2011b). Ecuador exemplifies this, with its economic dependency on extractivism widely accepted in public and political discourse (Acosta, 2013; Arsel et al., 2016b).

In the presence of a dominant narrative of dependence, what approaches might foster a social-ecological transformation that is rooted in social and environmental justice? Particularly intriguing are instances where anti-extractive movements have been widely accepted or achieved significant victories, such as the Yasuni, as these cases may offer valuable insights into successful narrative shifts. Despite social relevance, there remains a notable gap in scholarly literature concerning the specific role of counter-hegemonic narratives in driving such transformative movements. While theories abound on the power of narratives for social change, research is needed that directly connects these theories to real-world cases like the Yasuni referendum.

Now, as the world handles the urgent need to break free from extractive practices amidst growing social-ecological conflicts and climate crises, attention turns to theories of social transformation to understand how a (post-extractivist) transformation could be steered. Some theories point toward the power of narratives in promoting social change. Scholars across several fields argue that the way we frame an issue, imagine the future, and narrate the change we desire is crucial to either transforming or stagnating societal structures (e.g., Beckert, 2013; Jeffrey & Dyson, 2021; Leach et al., 2010b; Wittmayer et al., 2015; Wright, 2013, etc.). Theories on narratives and social transformation deem (counter-hegemonic) narratives as a relevant element to promote societal change (Beckert, 2013; Wittmayer et al., 2015). While theories highlight the significance of collective narratives in driving societal change, limited research exists on the core components that constitute counter-hegemonic narratives and whether actors themselves view narratives as crucial.

Therefore, this thesis seeks to fill this gap by examining how counter-hegemonic narratives, as exemplified in the case of the Ecuadorian referendum for banning the oil exploitation in the Yasuni National Park, contribute to imagining and promoting post-extractivist transformations. Drawing on the methodological framework of case study research outlined by Yin (2017), this study aims to analyse the narratives that

emerged during the Yasuni referendum campaign and how they contribute to imagining and promoting post-extractive futures. Additionally, by incorporating perspectives from experts involved in the referendum and other data sources, this research aims to shed light on the perceived role of counter-hegemonic narratives in challenging dominant discourses and fostering societal change.

This research represents a commitment to understanding and advancing narratives of hope, resistance, and transformation in the face of extractive hegemony. Through analysis and thoughtful engagement with theory and practice, this thesis seeks to contribute to ongoing discussions on the possibilities for a just, equitable, and sustainable future.

2 Research Questions and Approach

This thesis focuses on the role of counter-hegemonic narratives in promoting a post-extractivist transformation by conducting case study research on the Ecuadorian national people's referendum for banning oil exploitation in the ITT block in the Yasuni National Park that took place on the 20th of August 2023. To do so, the main research question and three sub-research questions with respective objectives that were formulated to guide the research are:

How can counter-hegemonic narratives, as exemplified in the 2023 Yasuni-ITT referendum, contribute to imagining and promoting a post-extractivist transformation?

I. What key elements define the counter-hegemonic narratives around the 2023 Yasuni referendum?

This sub-research question aims to explore the framings and main elements used in counter-hegemonic narratives around the 2023 Yasuni referendum by collectives and experts that form part of the movement promoting the conservation of the Yasuni National Park.

II. How do these narratives envision a post-extractivist transformation?

The objective of the second sub-research question is to examine how counter-hegemonic narratives offer alternative visions of the future and challenge dominant hegemonic ideologies in the case of the Yasuni referendum to stop oil exploitation in the Yasuni National Park.

III. What significance do stakeholders within counter-extractivist movements attribute to narratives?

The third sub-research question aims to understand experts' perceptions of the importance of counter-hegemonic narratives in challenging dominant discourses and promoting social change.

The research question and the three sub-research questions were formulated to provide a clear framework for investigating the topic at hand. They guided the research through defining a methodology, data collection, data analysis, results presentation, and discussion.

The sub-research questions provided structure in the data collection and analysis process to focus on critical elements and create a coherent story while remaining focused on the main research question. This thesis aims to highlight narratives' role in a post-extractivist transformation, an abstract topic. Doing so could contribute to the existing literature on narratives for social change, social-ecological transformation, post-extractivism, and other similar fields, as well as provide a unique and historically relevant case study of the counter-extractivist movement.

The thesis structure is organized into six main sections to explore the research topic comprehensively. First, the **Methodology** section outlines the research design, including case study research, constructivist grounded theory, narrative inquiry, and data collection methods. Second, the **Theoretical Background** introduces key concepts and frameworks, such as narratives, hegemony, theories of social transformation, and discussions on extractivism and post-extractivism. Third, the **Case Contextualization** situates the Yasuni referendum within its historical, social, and national context to provide essential background. Fourth, the **Results** are presented in alignment with the three sub-research questions, offering a detailed analysis of the findings. Fifth, the **Discussion** interprets the results within the broader theoretical and practical context. Finally, the **Conclusion and Recommendations for Further Research** summarize the key insights and propose directions for future studies.

3 Methodology

This section explains the methodology used in this thesis, including the research design, case study selection, data collection and data analysis, limitations, and ethical considerations. A qualitative research approach was adopted for this thesis, using a single-case study research design as presented by Yin (2017).

Case study research was chosen because of its focus on an in-depth understanding of specific social phenomena, openness to multiple data sources, and its qualitative and reflective nature (Yin, 2017). The case study focused on the Ecuadorian people's referendum for ending oil exploitation in the ITT-Block in the Yasuni National Park that took place on August 20th, 2023. The case study is an example that helps approach and understand how counter-hegemonic narratives contribute to imagining and promoting post-extractivist transformations, which is an abstract topic.

3.1 Data Analysis

Data analysis began during the collection phase and guided the final stages of data inclusion (see Figure 1). Data analysis followed a constructivist grounded theory approach, as outlined by Charmaz (2017) and Mills et al. (2006), allowing theoretical insights to emerge from the data while remaining sensitive to the context and perspectives of participants, as well as recognizing the role of researcher interpretation in the process. This approach was selected for its suitability in critical inquiry, as it supports an open and sensitive analysis of participants' narratives (Charmaz, 2017; Mills et al., 2006). While findings are contextually specific to the case study—the Ecuadorian referendum to ban oil exploitation in Yasuni National Park—efforts were made to enhance the transferability of results.

Narrative inquiry methodology was also included in the analysis process. According to Bochner and Riggs (2014), narrative analysis should aim to establish the social and historical context relevant to the case at hand. This contextualization can be achieved by closely examining various elements of the material—words, sentences, paragraphs, and the overall message—and relating these elements to the themes and patterns relevant to the research question. Narrative analysis focuses on how people use stories to make sense of their experiences and the world around them. This method, therefore, examines the structure, content, and function of narratives to understand how individuals construct identities and social realities (Bochner & Riggs, 2014).

Researchers such as Welch & Piekkari (2006) have emphasized the importance of analysing data in its original language, as when important information is translated, the original meaning can be lost in translation or altered. Therefore, if possible, the analysis of data should be conducted in the same language as it was collected (Welch & Piekkari, 2006). This study's analysis and coding were conducted in Spanish to preserve the original forms of expression and wording found in the data. Results were only translated into English post-analysis and only to introduce direct quotes as part of the presentation of results. With the exception of quotes from E5 which was conducted in English, the citations presented as part of the results were translated by the author of the thesis.

Transcriptions and Documents were coded using the MaxQDA software application for qualitative analysis. The analysis involved an iterative coding process, identifying connections between narratives, socio-political understandings, and framings of the case at hand. Following (Strauss, 1987, p. 27) recommendations, *“Codes serve as shorthand devices to label, separate, compile, and organize data.”* In grounded theory, coding is a dynamic, iterative process essential for developing theory from qualitative data (Charmaz, 2017). This process entails three steps: dividing the data into concepts through open coding, linking these concepts during axial coding, and, finally, identifying a core category to refine and develop the theory through selective coding. This approach allows grounded theory researchers to establish theoretical foundations and generate insights significant to their fields (Charmaz, 2017). Throughout the coding process, memos were regularly written to capture key ideas or observations that emerged, which is an essential practice in both case study research and grounded theory methodology (Charmaz, 2017; Yin, 2017).

After several rounds of coding, the selective coding process guided the identification of key themes in the data. While a significant number of codes and topics emerged, the analysis was refined to focus on the narratives most relevant to the research question. These results will be presented in detail in Section 6, following the theoretical framework and a contextual overview of the case study.

3.2 Research Design

Case study research involves a systematic and iterative process of planning, collecting, analysing, and interpreting data related to a specific case (Yin, 2017), as shown in Figure 1. According to Yin (2017), a case study as a research method can be defined twofold. First, by focusing on the scope of a case study, where *“A case study is an empirical method that Investigates a contemporary phenomenon (the ‘case’) in depth and within its real-world context especially when the boundaries between phenomenon and context*

may not be clearly evident” (Yin, 2017, p. 15). Secondly, turning to the features of a case, explaining that “A case study copes with the technically distinctive situation in which there will be many more variables of interest than data points, and as a result benefits from the prior development of theoretical propositions to guide design, data collection, and analysis, and as another result relies on multiple sources of evidence, with data needing to converge in a triangulating fashion” (Yin, 2017, p. 15).

This definition fits well with the topic at hand. For instance, the national referendum for ending oil extraction from the ITT block in the Yasuni National Park is a current, unique, well-known, and relevant case in the field of direct democracy and environmental politics (Aguilera Bravo & C3n3dor Salazar, 2010; Brito, 2020; High, 2020; News Wires, 2023), where the researcher had no control over the events being studied. Additionally, the referendum results from part of a longer process of environmental and social protection movements. Hence, it needs to be understood within the national and local contexts where it is placed, making the boundaries between phenomenon and context unclear. It creates a large number of variables of interest. In addition, the formulated research objectives require an in-depth understanding of a social phenomenon to reveal insights, patterns, and underlying factors that may not be evident through other research methods. To achieve this, the research design included multiple sources of information for triangulation and considered existing theoretical frameworks to shape its data collection and analysis processes. A case study research design is consequently well-suited for this thesis.

Figure 1: Case Study Research Process - adapted from Yin (2017, p.2)

It is important to note that the research focus is set on the role of counter-hegemonic narratives in promoting post-extractivist transformations, as exemplified by the case study at hand. Therefore, while the research design is case study research, the author has also included elements of narrative inquiry- as

presented by Bochner & Herrmann (2020)- during the data collection and analysis processes. Including narrative inquiry was key to keeping the analysis focused and sensible to the features of the data that create framings of the world, the way the story is told, and narratives as created by people.

Narrative inquiry, initially developed within the field of psychology, has, over the past two decades, become a common methodology in qualitative research across the social sciences. While traditionally focused on the experiences of singular individuals, this approach can also be applied to groups of actors (Bochner & Herrmann, 2020). In this thesis, I conceptualize narratives as deeply personal, changeable, and situated within each individual's unique context. Specifically, I define "counter-hegemonic narratives" as the collection of plural and unique stories that align in their opposition to extractivism, particularly the exploitation of the ITT block in the Yasuní National Park.

Narrative inquiry invites the development of reflexive, dialogic, and interpretative methodologies that focus on the actual and the possible by placing people, meaning, and personal identity at the centre of research (Bochner & Herrmann, 2020). Here, storytelling is seen as *"the means by which we represent our experiences to ourselves and others; it is how we make sense of our lives and fill them with meaning"* (Bochner & Herrmann, 2020, p. 286). To study the narrative is to study persons as beings existing in a socially constructed narrative shaped by stories. Hence, a key feature is that stories hold in them the way we "reckon with time" (Bochner & Herrmann, 2020). Storytelling shows that we are historical beings living in a present shaped by the weight of the past and influenced by the uncertainty of the future. Bochner & Herrmann (2020) further highlight that we find ourselves in a process where we are *"living out and through our storied existence"* (Bochner & Herrmann, 2020, p. 287). It is possible to re-story our lives by revisiting meanings and constructing new storylines that help exert agency and control over the possibilities, ambiguities, and limitations.

It is, therefore, in the narratives that the object of study is found. These *narratives-under-analysis*, as Bochner & Herrmann (2020) call them, is the study of narratives as the means to explore and understand a wide range of sense-making experiences. For example, in this thesis, the data analysis focused on how certain events are presented and which words are being used, as it is in the story-telling that one can explore the meaning that something holds for a person or a collective.

3.3 Case Selection

The present study employs a single-case study design, focusing on the Ecuadorian referendum banning oil exploitation in the ITT-Block in the Yasuni National Park, held on August 20th, 2023 (CNE, 2023b). This case, referred to as the Yasuni referendum in this thesis, was selected for its exemplary characteristics, unique context, and theoretical relevance, making it an appropriate and valuable case for exploring narratives and their role in post-extractivism in Ecuador. Therefore, it is considered a case of revelatory nature, which, according to Yin (2017), is a strong rationale for choosing a single case over multiple cases.

The Yasuni referendum represents an exemplary environmental democracy and post-extractivist decision-making (Brito, 2020; News Wires, 2023). This case stands out globally as the first instance of direct environmental democracy (News Wires, 2023), with Ecuadorians exercising their constitutional rights in a national, obligatory vote to protect one of the world's most biodiverse regions of the planet (Bass et al., 2010).

The case is also set in a unique context, with several aspects that make it stand out nationally and internationally. First, the referendum is connected to a decision that impacts one of the most biodiverse places in the world and the presence of Indigenous groups, including those in voluntary isolation (Bass et al., 2010; Finer et al., 2009). Second, the referendum is grounded in an extensive history of land, social, and environmental protection movements (Le Quang, 2016; Mancilla & Martínez, 2014), with its importance recognized on an international level and well-documented in academic literature (e.g. Dyar, 2014; Kingsbury et al., 2019; Laastad, 2024; Mila Maldonado et al., 2024, etc.). Lastly, it presents a unique opportunity to investigate direct environmental democracy within Ecuador's constitutional principles of *Sumak Kawsay* (Buen Vivir), which recognize the rights of nature and indigenous peoples (Arteaga-Cruz, 2017).

For the reasons presented above, this case is considered to hold significant theoretical relevance. According to the theoretical framework adopted in this study, which explores the role of narratives in a post-extractivist transformation, the Yasuni referendum offers an ideal context for examining key variables such as counter-hegemonic narratives and environmental movements. The referendum sparked a moment of national debate about oil extractivism and modes of development in Ecuador and won, with 58% of voters supporting the closure of the ITT block (CNE, 2023b). Diverse grassroots movements primarily drove the history and campaign for the referendum (Mancilla & Martínez, 2014; Mila Maldonado et al., 2024) representing a counter-hegemonic stance in a complex socio-political context that embodies

the tensions of post-extractivist discourses in a resource-extracting country like Ecuador. The case also embodies long-standing tensions between development and conservation, making it a representative example of the global challenges facing biodiversity hotspots and Indigenous rights (Finer et al., 2009).

The boundaries of this case study are defined by the referendum on banning oil exploitation in Yasuni National Park, held alongside general elections on August 20th, 2023 (CNE, 2023a), rather than the more extensive history of the ITT initiative itself. While the study considers the history and key events leading to the referendum, the data used for analysis is guided by clear inclusion criteria for each data source. Therefore, the data included in this research is directly connected to the narratives surrounding the 2023 Yasuni referendum. This approach ensures a focused examination of the dynamics shaping narratives and key messages in Ecuador.

3.4 Data Collection

The data collection process was guided by the research aims, considering the limitations present in the possibilities for data collection. Multiple sources of evidence, a practice known as triangulation, were used to achieve this. As Yin (2017, p. 126) states, *“A major strength of case study data collection is the opportunity to use many different sources of evidence.”* Utilizing multiple sources is a critical methodological practice to develop converging lines of inquiry. By gathering information from diverse sources, this study aimed to enhance the validity and reliability of its findings, offering a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon under investigation (Yin, 2017). The primary reason for employing triangulation was to conduct an in-depth study of the phenomenon within its real-world context, which was crucial for this thesis.

Given the time, spatial, and capacity limitations, the data collection involved gathering qualitative data from four sources. The primary data source consisted of expert interviews, which provided a closer view of the experiences, opinions, and worldviews of people directly involved in the case. These experts also offered valuable insights into the broader public narratives shaped by their work, experience, or interactions with diverse stakeholders.

The expert interview data was complemented by three other sources, including press conferences, press releases from key social groups, and document analysis. These additional sources were essential to providing a broader context and highlighting collective narratives beyond the individual perspectives shared by experts. These sources added depth and a richer understanding of the case's social and political dynamics.

Considering the focus of the research on the role of counter-hegemonic narratives, the data selected was from experts and sources advocating for the conservation of Yasuni National Park and the closure of the ITT block. The Yasuni National Park conservation narrative is considered a counter-hegemonic narrative, in contrast to the government and elite groups that support oil exploitation within the park. This selection was driven by the formulated research aims, aligning with the goals of narrative analysis. Additionally, this thesis's theoretical background section will give an insight into the contents of the hegemonic narrative—which supports oil extraction.

During the data collection process, a comprehensive case study database was created in Microsoft Excel to maintain an organized overview of the research process. Data from interviews and press conferences was transcribed, and all data was compiled into a MaxQDA file, a program chosen for its ability to support in-depth qualitative analysis. Transcription was initially done using the online tool Turboscribe.ai, followed by careful manual correction to ensure accuracy.

3.4.1 Semi-Structured expert interviews

Interviews were conducted with key stakeholders involved in the national Yasuni referendum, these interviews aimed to capture a range of perspectives and narratives surrounding the oil extraction and banning further exploitation of the ITT block, offering insights from various stakeholders "from the inside." The focus of these interviews aligns with narrative research, seeking to explore the stories propagated by different groups and individuals involved in the referendum process and their perceptions of the role of narratives in societal transformation.

The inclusion criteria for expert interviews adopted a broad understanding of "experts" beyond academic scholars. The selection focused on individuals who actively supported the conservation of Yasuni National Park and the closure of the ITT block, as well as those who were directly connected to and engaged in the election process of the Yasuni referendum. Based on these criteria, 51 experts were identified and contacted. The response was limited; there were time restrictions and other planning difficulties. Eight expert interviews (E) were conducted, as presented in Table 1 below. The limited response, primarily from academics based in Quito, introduces a potential bias. However, it also represents the context, as academic discussions about Yasuni are often concentrated in specific circles in the capital.

The interviews varied in length and were primarily conducted online and in Spanish, except one in English and one in person. The types of experts interviewed ranged from academics to activists, offering diverse insights. The information collected from interviews is presented anonymously, per the request of some participants, to protect their positions and ensure their safety.

Additionally, an exploratory interview was conducted with a member of the YASunidos collective, which proved helpful in identifying key topics for developing the list of questions used in the expert interviews. For example, during this interview, it became clear that asking participants to describe their wishes for the future was too broad, abstract, and personal, prompting a refinement of the questionnaire to be more specific in the questions.

Table 1: Expert Interview Information

ID	Background	Length	Date
E0	Explorative Interview	22:46	06/06/2024
E1	Political Economy, Development Studies	55:35	28/06/2024
E2	Environmental Sciences and Biology	36:48	10/07/2024
E3	Sociology, Latin-American and Feminist Studies	33:12	12/07/2024
E4	Sociology, Development Studies	35:04	01/08/2024
E5	Environmental Sciences and Conservation	44:13	02/08/2024
E6	Psychology, collective health	22:28	07/08/2024
E7	International and development studies, anthropology	45:31	09/09/2024
E8	Law, Indigenous leader	31:05	25/07/2024

The interviews were semi-structured, using an open questionnaire designed to encourage experts to share their stories and highlight what they considered most relevant—particularly related to the Yasuni-ITT case and the referendum's victory. Part of the questions focused on understanding the experts' positionality and expertise regarding the case. Experts were asked what the Yasuni or the Yasuni referendum represents for them, their perceptions of narratives present in Ecuador, and, in some cases, about the possibility of a post-extractivist transformation. To conclude the interview, experts were asked a question directly addressing the role of narratives, specifically how they perceive the power of imagining the future and envisioning utopian possibilities.

3.4.2 Complementary data sources

Three additional sources complemented the expert interview data, including 1) press conferences, 2) press releases issued by key groups or actors involved in the case, and 3) document analysis, which included campaign materials and documents that experts identified as important for the context of this thesis. Documents included plans and proposals from collectives, presentations, and *amicus curiae*² briefs. These complementary sources were essential in providing a broader context and offering an overview of collective narratives, which supplemented the individual perspectives shared by the experts.

The inclusion of these complementary sources followed specific criteria. Press conferences (PC) and press releases (PR) were selected based on their relevance to key groups and the timing of their release. Press conferences and releases took place between the time the referendum was announced in June 2023, the results on the 21st of August 2023, and those published on the referendum's anniversary in August 2024. Document analysis focused on the main campaign materials and materials mentioned or shared by the experts during the interviews. Table 2 presents more information about the complementary data sources used for triangulation.

Table 2: Complementary Data Information

ID	Title (translated from Spanish)	Author	Date
Press Releases			
PR1	We celebrate the triumph of the 'Yes' for Yasuní and the Andean Chocó	CONAIE	23/08/2023
PR2	Communication from the Amazon Youth on the Lasso government's statements on the results of the referendum on Yasuní ITT block 43	Collective of young defenders of the Amazonia	24/08/2023
PR3	Press Release NAWE Yasuni Summit	NAWE	n.a
PR4	Noboa makes a mockery of the popular mandate	YASunidos	28/08/2024
PR5	One year of non-fulfilment	YASunidos	16/08/2024
Press Conferences			
PC1	Press conference on the results of the Yasuní referendum	Various groups and collectives	21/08/2023
PC2	"Yes" to Yasuni: representatives of the seven nationalities	Indigenous Groups	27/07/2023
PC3	The Union of People Affected by Texaco (UDAPT) in the context of the People's Consultation for Yasuni	UDAPT	05/07/2023

² one (such as a professional person or organization) that is not a party to a particular litigation but that is permitted by the court to advise it in respect to some matter of law that directly affects the case in question (Miriam Webster Dictionary)

PC4	Cuenca: Communities of the Amazon and the Yasunidos Collective hold a press conference in support of the Yes vote in the referendum on Yasuní.	YASunidos and Amazonian communities	15/08/2023
Documents			
D1	<i>Amicus Curiae</i>	Carlos Larrea	04/2023
D2	<i>Amicus Curiae</i>	Wilma Salgado	04/2023
D3	Plan Yasuni-Ten ideas for discussing the ecological transition to a post-oil Ecuador	YASunidos/Scientific Rebellion Abya Yala	07/2023
D4	Plan C: Redistribution of Wealth to Avoid Exploiting the Yasuní and Safeguard Isolated Indigenous Peoples	CDES	08/2013
D5	Plans from A to Z. YASunidos for the referendum	YASunidos	10/11/2013
D6	Book: Yasunidos- Political imagination and society in movement	YASunidos	12/02/2020
D7	Waorani mandate for closure, dismantling, ecological restoration and social reparation in the Yasuni	NAWE	01/08/2024
D8	Flyer: Yes to Yasuni	Si al Yasuni	07/2023
D9	Brochure: Everything you want to know about Yasuni and the referendum	Si al Yasuni	07/ 2023

The rationale for incorporating these additional data sources was to enrich the analysis and complement the expert interview data. Press conferences offered an opportunity to capture collective narratives and highlight the voices of groups, particularly Indigenous groups, which was challenging to achieve through expert interviews. Similarly, press releases provided insights into the clear messages and key topics emphasized by the organizations involved, offering a broader understanding of their objectives, demands, and wishes.

Moreover, document analysis complemented the analysis by showcasing proposals, arguments, and main campaign messages, especially those produced by YASunidos. These documents not only highlighted the groups' main concerns and messages but also helped contextualize their clear proposals and wishes for the future of the Yasuni and the country. Campaign materials revealed the strategies and key messages used to engage the public. Hence, Document analysis further contributed to understanding the story, including the arguments and counterarguments presented in response to the dominant discourse surrounding the referendum.

3.5 Methodological Limitations

This study faced limitations that need to be acknowledged. Firstly, due to logistical constraints, I - the researcher- was not physically present in Ecuador for the data collection process. This created a reliance on online sources and communication channels. This approach may have limited the ability to contact

experts and access information, particularly considering the challenges of online communication, time zone differences, and the benefits of missed face-to-face interviews.

Secondly, some limitations in the interviewing process were recognised. For example, the interviews were brief due to the difficulty of online communication and other barriers, such as the limited free time of experts and the inability to offer some remuneration. This time limitation restricted the possibility of clarifying or elaborating with experts on some of their opinions or perceptions. Another aspect relates to saturation; defining a clear saturation point is challenging due to the inherently individual nature of narratives. Additionally, time constraints limited the possibility of collecting data over an extended period. However, responses were obtained from a diverse range of participants, which helped to mitigate this limitation. To further enhance the robustness of the findings, multiple data sources were incorporated into the study through triangulation.

Third, all data - except for one interview- was collected in Spanish and had to be translated into English for the writing process. It is important to recognize that some meaning might be lost in the translation process and that the translation could not be perfect. The author of this thesis is a native Spanish speaker, so content revisions were made carefully to ensure that the translation is as accurate as possible.

Finally, the research methods were carefully selected for this topic and within the acknowledged limitations to align with the study's objectives. Nevertheless, ethnographic methods could provide additional insights, offering a more immersive approach to understanding narratives and their contextual nuances.

It is important to consider these methodological limitations when interpreting the findings of this study. They should be factored into any overall assessment of the study's conclusions to ensure a balanced understanding of its contributions and constraints.

3.6 Ethical considerations

Ethical principles, including informed consent, confidentiality, and respect for participant autonomy, were upheld throughout all data collection, processing, analysis, and writing. All personal data and information that could identify specific experts were anonymized to ensure these principles were maintained, particularly after two participants explicitly requested anonymity. Consent to record and transcribe the interviews was also sought. These steps were taken to safeguard ethical considerations and the safety of participants.

Additionally, the researcher was mindful of their positionality and possible bias throughout the research. As an Ecuadorian student in Austria, I bring a unique perspective to this study. Growing up in Ecuador, I am familiar with its political and cultural context. However, I must acknowledge that I am not part of certain significant groups and ethnicities for this research. While Spanish is my native language and the official language of Ecuador, I have limited knowledge of other languages spoken by various cultural groups in the country, such as Waorani, which is spoken in the Yasuni region.

My positionality provides me with a unique understanding and closeness to the topic under study. However, it is equally important to acknowledge that it may introduce biases in certain aspects of the research, particularly those shaped by my background as an urban, mixed-race individual engaged in international studies. A grounded theory approach was employed as the foundation for the analytical process to address the potential for subjectivity in the analysis, ensuring a systematic and reflective engagement with the data.

4 Theoretical Background

This section aims to present the theoretical foundation for this thesis. The data analysis of this research adopted a constructivist grounded theory approach (Charmaz, 2017a). Therefore, the theoretical framework supports only by setting the context and definitions for research design and data collection and resurfaces in the final stages of discussion and conclusion to link findings from a singular and unique case study to a broader context, thus employing theory to generalize case studies, as advocated by Yin (2017).

As the thesis research focuses on the role of counter-hegemonic narratives in driving a post-extractivist transformation, the theoretical background was divided into two main areas: the role of narratives in driving societal transformations and post-extractivism. In this section, the concepts of hegemony and counter-hegemony were also considered and included in the different areas. By presenting these theoretical backgrounds, this section lays the groundwork for understanding the context in which the research design was created, defining important concepts, and interpreting findings.

4.1 Narratives

This research focuses on the role of counter-hegemonic narratives in a post-extractivist transformation, using elements of narrative inquiry for data analysis. From a methodological perspective, narrative inquiry emphasizes reflexive, dialogic, and interpretative methods that focus on the role of narratives on people, meaning, and identity. It views storytelling as a way to represent experiences, make sense of life, and navigate time as historical beings shaped by the past and future (Bochner & Herrmann, 2020). So, narratives – through storytelling- enable individuals to revisit meanings, construct new storylines, and exert agency over doubts, wishes, and limitations. Various disciplines have explored narratives and storytelling's linguistic and discursive aspects, highlighting their importance for individuals and societies across fields having its beginnings in psychology (Bochner & Herrmann, 2020; Wittmayer et al., 2015, 2015).

In this thesis, I focus on a select number of theories that contextualize the topic by linking narratives to societal transformations. These theories are mainly categorized as socio-economic theories of human behaviour, which emphasize the transformative role of narratives in society and are known under various terms, including *narratives of change* (Wittmayer et al., 2015), *fictional expectations* (Beckert, 2013), *concrete and real utopias* (Levitas, 1990; Wright, 2013), and *prefigurative politics* (Jeffrey & Dyson, 2021).

Theories within the context of narrative research are broad and multidisciplinary, encompassing diverse schools of thought with varying ontological and epistemological assumptions. For this thesis, I adopt a constructivist approach – viewing narratives as socially constructed and sustained – as proposed by Wittmayer et al. (2015). This approach facilitates tracing the social production of a narrative and exploring its role in societal change processes beyond its content (Schneider, 2019). Here, narratives are seen as stories we create that explain the world around us and inform decisions based on our comprehension of the present and visions for the future (Beckert, 2013; Schneider, 2019). According to Wittmayer et al. (2015, p.5), narratives of change are defined as "*sets of ideas, concepts, metaphors, discourses, or storylines about change and innovation,*" considering them a discursive form that positions actors within a given context and assigns events or activities a (temporal) sequence toward a specific goal or imagined future (Wittmayer et al., 2015). So, narratives are fundamental to understanding the world and its processes.

Moreover, narratives are socially produced and constructed and serve as both the medium and outcome of one's actions. Here, narratives are regarded as "*momentous co-constructions of narrators and audiences,*" simultaneously reflecting and creating reality (Wittmayer et al., 2015, p. 6). Hence, narratives exemplify a duality of agency and structure. Narratives result from widespread and sustained practices and gain influence by recruiting practitioners. Simultaneously, individuals can decide to reproduce or change an existing narrative based on their own beliefs and value systems (Wittmayer et al., 2015).

4.1.1 Hegemony in Narratives

Multiple narratives coexist simultaneously on various issues, with dominant narratives exerting influence over marginalized counter-narratives; this dynamic is inherently a matter of power (Schneider, 2019). Drawing on Gramsci's concept of hegemony, political elites seek to garner consent from civil society for their objectives, establishing ideological domination through widely accepted "common senses" (Gramsci, 1992). Although not necessarily objectively true, these common senses can be socially constructed and endorsed. In this context, certain narratives are emphasized, while others are marginalized or suppressed.

For instance, Brand & Wissen (2012) employ this Gramscian notion to illustrate how certain practices, such as the *imperial mode of living*, have become normalized in capitalist societies, with the state serving as an "educator," propagating narratives to the civil population. The article discusses the concept of the imperial mode of living, referring to a dominant way of life rooted in capitalist production and consumption patterns. This mode of living is tied to ideas and narratives of progress, often disregarding

social and ecological consequences. The imperial mode of living becomes hegemonic when widely accepted and institutionally supported. The state plays a central role in sustaining this mode of living by ensuring access to resources abroad and maintaining domestic living standards through social policies. Dominant social groups use the state as a platform to establish hegemony by promoting growth and progress, framing these as societal norms.

Hegemonic narratives often invoke the TINA principle (There-Is-No-Alternative), limiting the consideration of alternatives, such as post-extractivism, in political and policy discourse. This phenomenon is described as *the colonization of the imaginary* by Latouche (2004) or *existing mental infrastructure* by Welzer (2011). Both concepts refer to deeply ingrained cultural and psychological frameworks that shape how societies and individuals perceive and prioritize economic growth, consumption, and progress, often reinforcing unsustainable and exploitative practices. They argue that hegemonic framings of the world, social norms, and future developments also impact the individual imaginary (Latouche, 2004; Welzer, 2011). Creating and understanding existing narratives and identifying alternative pathways are essential to overcome this (Schneider, 2019).

Counter-hegemonic narratives play a crucial role in re-politicizing debates on social-ecological transformation. Grassroots initiatives for societal change often have underlying *narratives of change* that shape behaviour and empower individuals and social innovation (Wittmayer et al., 2015). Scholars argue that by seeking new storylines, we can embrace alternative narratives and inspire change toward sustainable futures (Schneider, 2019). Hence, circular narratives, also known as "spiralling narratives" and "soft revolutions," embody transformative processes of change, breaking through mental blockades by identifying and communicating stories. Circular narratives offer transformative revolutionary processes by creatively building pathways within self-constructing networks (Schneider, 2019).

4.1.2 Significance of Narratives in Theories of Social-ecological Transformation

Having established that narratives are socially co-constructed and shaped by our perceptions and understandings of the world and the power dynamics inherent in hegemony, I now link these concepts to theories of transformation.

The necessity for social-ecological transformation arises from recognizing the presence of "multiple crises," including climate change, biodiversity loss, social conflicts, and resource depletion, amongst others. Görg et al. (2017) present social-ecological transformation as a concept that highlights the interplay between societal and environmental systems, focusing on their interdependencies and conflicts.

The concept points out the necessity of fundamental changes in societal relations to nature, moving toward sustainability through analytical and strategic approaches. Such transformation involves a reconfiguration of societal structures, practices, and values (Görg et al., 2017). Social-ecological transformation stems primarily from the disciplines of Social Ecology and Political Ecology, which explore societal relationships with nature, power dynamics, and resource use patterns. These disciplines provide insights into the structural and power-related barriers to sustainability and the contested processes involved in transformations (Görg et al., 2017), such as a post-extractivist transformation.

Some theories suggest that narratives hold significance in steering or stagnating social-ecological transformations as actors and institutions commit to or reconfigure specific societal structures, practices, and values. Narratives are deemed to play a pivotal role in "the politics of signification," namely, the production and maintenance of meaning in the context of societal change, culture, and practices (Wittmayer et al., 2015). Leach et al. (2010) argue that a specific narrative offers a particular framing of a system and its dynamics. When someone believes in a narrative, it simultaneously suggests how the system should evolve or transform to achieve a desired set of outcomes. Thus, *"narratives of change are not merely 'stories out there,' but rather recount the theories of change practised and acted upon by the very social innovation initiatives that propagate them"* (Wittmayer et al., 2015, pp. 15-16).

Narratives of change evoke imagination and invite actors to think from *what-is* to *what-if*, opening new possibilities for the future. Therefore, narratives can be seen as part of social innovations. They suggest and constitute (new) alternative ways of framing the world. Stories can shape behaviour and serve as powerful sources of change, playing three key roles: triggering imagination, expressing (counter-) cultures, and empowering individuals (Wittmayer et al., 2015). This process is how *"changes in stories at a specific level have consequences for stories at another level"* (Wittmayer et al., 2015, p.7). Narratives may exhibit relative stability and habitual characteristics but also emerge as situational reactions in each context (Leach et al., 2010b; Wittmayer et al., 2015, 2019).

Wittmayer et al. (2015) suggest a method for reconstructing and analysing narratives of change where one must focus on three elements: the content, the role, and the production of narratives. By looking into these elements, the analysis can understand the role of narratives in spreading alternative views, ideas, and practices and how networks use them to increase their transformative potential towards dominant and institutionalised notions and practices (Wittmayer et al., 2015).

Furthermore, Beckert (2013) connects narratives to economic theory, arguing that a significant portion of economic decisions is grounded in fictionalities and personal assumptions, emphasizing that narratives are fundamental to understanding the possibilities for change. Beckert (2013) calls narratives a "fictionality" that provides a way of understanding the micro-foundations and dynamics of the economy. The author argues that we base most of our economic decisions on fictional expectations and not rational ones, so images of the future shape present decisions rather than a calculation of optimal choices. Thus, *"Stories provide causal links that show how the gap between the present state of the world and the predicted future state is actually closed"* (Beckert, 2013, pp. 226-227). Beckert's theory accepts fundamental uncertainty due to the "unknown and unknowable" nature of future events and rejects ideas of rational calculations that "accurately" anticipate the future. Beckert (2013), therefore, proposes that expectations are intrinsically fictional as they are based on pretensions of the future states of the world and what is believed to be accurate by an individual. Hence, it is in recognizing the human capability of imagining possible future states of the world that one finds a basis for connecting a theory of the capitalist economy to a theory of action. This so-called "sociological fictionalism" could form a crucial foundation for understanding how social cooperation dilemmas are overcome (Beckert, 2013).

The theory of fictional expectations emphasizes the role of institutions or cultural frames that motivate actors through an internalized desire to conform to social norms (Beckert, 2013). Hence, social macrostructures – networks, institutions, and cultural frameworks- are key to the emergence and stability of fictional expectations and narratives of change (Beckert, 2013; Wittmayer et al., 2015). Institutional structures can reduce uncertainty and support specific fictions, framings and narratives, while cultural frames can shape the direction of fictional expectations. The role of institutions is crucial in understanding how imaginaries or narratives gain traction and achieve "success" by being widely adopted and shared among larger social groups (Beckert, 2013; Wittmayer et al., 2015).

Moreover, Leach et al. (2010) look into *dynamic sustainabilities*, paying attention to how multiple, diverse framings and narratives bring vital opportunities to advance debates on sustainability and connect them more with questions of social justice. The authors argue that certain actors produce narratives and co-construct a specific response pathway, such as extractivism, as the only way of funding development. In this process, some dominant narratives might obscure others, and powerful actors and institutions tend to "close down" into specific framings, committing to pathways that emphasize maintaining stability and control. Leach et al. (2010) argue that narratives are an essential element in understanding systems of

pathway dependency, arguing that pathways are conditional to their underlying institutions and, therefore, their narratives and framings.

Formulating framings or narratives involves choosing which elements to highlight, a subjective process based on personal value judgments. Therefore, paying attention to how actors and networks produce- and sometimes seek to promote- particular framings is an important addition to systems perspectives, which tend to downplay the roles of some actors and their agency (Leach et al., 2010).

As discussed in this section, the theoretical link between narratives and social transformations is closely aligned with the use of stories, fictionalities, and imaginaries of the future. This comes from the understanding that individuals and institutions create specific narratives that, over time, actively shape and co-create the world we inhabit (Leach et al., 2010a; Wittmayer et al., 2019). Thus, the potential for change is closely tied to transforming existing narratives or constructing new, counter-hegemonic visions of the future. While not explicitly focused on narratives, two concepts—*prefigurative politics* and *concrete utopias*—offer valuable insights into imagined political futures and the role of fiction or utopias in driving change.

Concrete utopia is a concept employed when looking into alternatives to transforming dominant institutions and social structures. Whereas an abstract utopia is considered idealistic and divorced from reality, a concrete utopia is grounded in existing conditions and aspires towards a better future (Levitas, 1990). In this case, hope plays a key role as a driving force for social change and advocates for cultivating an "educated hope," which combines critical awareness with visionary imagination. A concrete utopia is, therefore, anticipatory rather than compensatory and builds on so-called "will-full" thinking (Levitas, 1990). This theory highlights the role of imagining future alternatives in societal transformations and transforming dominant institutions. It formulates utopias that can be conceived in concrete form by challenging dominant pathways.

Moreover, Jeffrey and Dyson (2021) examine the concept of *prefigurative politics in geographies of the future*, which involves envisioning and embodying the future within present political actions. This concept is commonly understood as "being the change you wish to see." Prefigurative politics refers to integrating the desired social relations, decision-making processes, culture, and human experiences into the current political practices of a movement. Therefore, prefigurative politics is seen as a spatial and performative form of political activism, where individuals enact a vision of change based on their expectations of the future (Jeffrey & Dyson, 2021). The act of creating, imagining, narrating, and formulating desires for the

future becomes a key point that connects the actions and narratives of the present with the possibilities for the future.

In summary, counter-hegemonic narratives play a focal role in shaping social-ecological transformations by influencing perceptions, values, and power dynamics. Their significance lies in their ability to reflect existing hegemonies and their potential to challenge and reimagine them, particularly through institutional co-creation of alternative futures.

4.2 Extractivism

This next part of the theoretical background centres on positioning extractivism and the elements characteristic of neo-extractivism in Latin America as the key entry point for analysis. Main concepts will be defined to situate the extractive system to the Latin American context.

A substantial body of literature delves into the intricacies of extractivism, its political context, global discourses, and manifestations across Latin America, including in Ecuador. Scholars such as Acosta (2013, 2017) and Gudynas (2019) concentrate on *neo-extractivism* and its connection to the so-called *resource curse* (Gilberthorpe & Rajak, 2017; Ross, 1999). Others, like Arsel et al. (2016a, 2016b) and Swallow (2017), scrutinize the emergence and nature of extractivism within leftist governments, termed the *extractive imperative*. Likewise, Svampa (2012, 2015) is a relevant researcher, especially in including the term *commodities consensus* in analysing the economic and political dependence on export products. The following section will present the theoretical basis and definition of extractivism and these important sub-definitions in current academic discussions.

Acosta (2013, p. 62) defines extractivism as *"those activities which remove large quantities of natural resources that are not processed (or processed only to a limited degree), especially for export."* This concept is not limited to minerals or petroleum; there are agricultural, forest, fishing, and touristic forms of extractivism (Gudynas, 2019). Scholars in Latin America - such as Acosta (2013), Gudynas (2011b), and Svampa (2012), among others - widely agree that extractivism extends beyond the activity of resource extraction, manifesting as a social phenomenon fraught with violence and territorial dispossession. This way, extractivism encompasses a distinct mode of accumulation and appropriation that becomes a fundamental pillar of primary export-driven accumulation within the framework of capitalism (Acosta, 2013; Arsel et al., 2016a). As Acosta (2017, para.13) explains, extractivism is a concept that informs *"processes of plundering, accumulation, concentration, and colonial and neocolonial devastation."* In this

context, extractivism is also closely connected to the evolution of modern capitalism and the notions of "development" and "underdevelopment." (Acosta, 2017)

The system of extractivism was established more than 500 years ago, as the processes of colonisation went hand in hand with the search for materials for extraction and export to Europe. The academic theory argues that much of the current structure of the world economy and the capitalist system was established during colonisation in America, Africa, and Asia (Acosta, 2001). The system was fundamentally shaped by a commodity-export or extractive accumulation model driven by demands originating from capitalist centres. Over time, specific regions, mainly in the Global South, specialized in extracting raw materials and primary goods, while others focused on manufacturing, often relying on the natural resources of economically disadvantaged nations (Acosta, 2013). This dynamic has established the reliance on primary export accumulation, with extractivism serving as a key manifestation of this process (Acosta, 2013).

Extractivism, characterized by the large-scale extraction and export of natural resources, typically benefits wealthier nations by supplying raw materials while leaving resource-exporting countries with environmental destruction, social displacement, and limited economic gains (Acosta, 2017; Roberts & Parks, 2009). This dynamic perpetuates the structural inequalities highlighted by *ecological unequal exchange*, where the Global South disproportionately shoulders the environmental burdens while the Global North reaps economic benefits (Hickel et al., 2022; Roberts & Parks, 2009). This way, world systems theory argues that international trade becomes a catalyst for inequality, serving as the primary mechanism for the accumulation of value and overconsumption in advanced regions, while other regions remain dependent on the production of resource- and labour-intensive goods that do not provide the same level economic freedom. Thus, it illustrates value appropriation through power imbalances within the global economy (Hickel et al., 2022; Roberts & Parks, 2009).

This world order has remained largely unchanged since the colonial era, drawing attention to the persistent "underdevelopment" of specific countries and their inability to enhance social well-being despite substantial revenues from material exports. Scholars have termed this phenomenon the *resource curse*, highlighting the paradox in which resource-rich nations frequently experience slower economic growth, weaker democratic institutions, and heightened levels of corruption compared to countries with fewer natural resources (Gilberthorpe & Rajak, 2017; Ross, 1999).

Ross (1999) elaborates on further economic and political aspects that could explain the prolonged emergence of the resource curse. On the economic side, the four most prominent explanations for the

course are a decline in trade for primary commodities since the 1980s, the instability of international commodity markets, and poor economic linkages between resource and non-resource sectors. These factors are accompanied by political elements present in countries with high natural resources (Ross, 1999). The three most important categories are short-sightedness among policymakers (especially connected to times of resource boom), resource exports often strengthening specific sectors or interest groups that advocate for policies hindering economic growth, and resource booms undermining the strength and effectiveness of state institutions (Ross, 1999).

The resource curse is an example of the difficulties connected with extractivism as a system that has created economic dependencies in producer countries, increased social inequality, and corruption (Acosta, 2017; Gilberthorpe & Rajak, 2017). Local impacts, both social and environmental, have accompanied this. However, scholars stress that the resource curse is not an inevitable fate but rather a choice and a path that can be changed (Acosta, 2017; Gudynas, 2011b).

4.2.1 Neo-extractivism

While the foundation of extractivism has remained unchanged for hundreds of years, academic articles reflect on the shifts that have been present. A decisive change happened when some progressive governments in South America acknowledged the problems associated with extractivism and proposed changes to the extractivist model (Acosta, 2013). Nevertheless, these efforts primarily aimed to address longstanding social demands and consolidate political power, often through clientelism and authoritarian practices. According to Gudynas (2011a), these governments introduced a "new type of extractivism," whereas the fundamental structure of accumulation remained unchanged. This neo-extractivism continued to subordinate exporting nations to the global economy, exacerbating territorial fragmentation and sustaining or worsening social and environmental impacts.

Gudynas (2011a) and Svampa (2015) highlight the role of the state in neoextractivism, particularly in progressive Latin American governments advocating for active state intervention to fund social policies through state-owned enterprises or augmented taxation of private companies. A key shift lies in the state's increased role, which seeks greater control over natural resources and their benefits, criticizing corporate dominance rather than extraction itself (Gudynas, 2011a). Neoextractivism also intersects with extractivism and neo-developmentalism by highlighting the dimension of financial capital. Financial entities increasingly profit from investments in extractive activities linked to creating new financial goods grounded in the privatization and exploitation of nature (Acosta, 2013). This system often accepts

environmental and social costs as necessary trade-offs for national development. States aim to capture a larger share of resource revenues to fund expansive social programs, reinforcing their social legitimacy (Svampa, 2015).

Commodities consensus

While the (new) development paradigm becomes dependent on extracting and importing primary commodities to global markets, it also creates a so-called *commodities consensus*. The commodity consensus underlines Latin America's entry into a new economic and political-ideological order, sustained by the boom in international commodity prices and consumer goods increasingly demanded by the core countries and emerging powers (Svampa, 2012, 2015).

This concept highlights how such focus on commodities shapes economic, political, and social dynamics. Svampa (2015, p. 67) explains that "*the commodities consensus is built on the idea that there is —tacit or explicit—agreement about the irrevocable or irresistible character of the current extractivist dynamic, resulting from growing global demand for raw materials.*" Arguing that, while the Washington Consensus prioritized financial valorisation, emphasizing adjustment and privatization policies. The commodities consensus focuses on the large-scale implementation of export-oriented extractive projects with a more flexible approach to the state's role. A defining feature of the commodities consensus is the surge in socio-environmental conflicts, especially those driven by land disputes and shared natural resources, as countries turn most of the focus on the export of commodities (Svampa, 2015).

The Extractive Imperative

Moreover, by focusing on some specific political dynamics of neo-extractivism, Arsel et al. (2016a, 2016b) argue that a so-called *extractive imperative* gets established. Arsel et al. (2016b) underscore two central components that build this imperative: 1) framing extraction as crucial and as the only way for economic structural transformation and 2) fostering extensive state involvement, linking resource extraction to social-populist projects to be funded by extractive revenues. The extractive imperative in Latin America is connected with the so-called Left Turn - this consists of a group of political parties known for its promises of regime shifts, political stability, and economic development for the country that called themselves "21st-century socialists". The Left Turn overlapped with a commodity boom, helping these governments implement their political agenda, break the dominance of past neoliberal practices, and give the state a protagonist role in extractive industries. The revenues were used in programs to tackle inequality and poverty and acquire international lending (Arsel et al., 2016b).

Various factors, including global demand for commodities, technological advancements in extraction techniques, and the influence of powerful multinational corporations, reinforce this extractive imperative (Arsel et al., 2016b). This imperative goes beyond "simple" extractivism; it is rooted in a widespread political and self-sustained ideology/zeitgeist, which plays a fundamental role in a development model that outlines expectations and policies (Arsel et al., 2016a). Bolivia, Venezuela, and Ecuador are seen as emblematic of the extractive imperative, with the State's prominent role in economic development and intensification of natural resource extraction during the past decades (Arsel et al., 2016a). Academic sources highlight the extractive imperative as a driver of various socio-economic and environmental challenges (Arsel et al., 2016a; León, 2017; Swallow, 2017). The expansion of extractive practices often results in ecosystems' degradation, loss of biodiversity, and disruption of Indigenous communities (Acosta, 2013; Arsel et al., 2016a).

4.2.2 The Hegemonic Nature of Extractivist Narratives

Extractivism is often characterized as a hegemonic system because of its prominent and resilient position in today's global and political order (Acosta, 2013; Acosta & Brand, 2018; Svampa, 2012). Furthermore, as both the commodities consensus and the extractive imperative demonstrate, the strength of the pro-extractivist agenda is very prominent in Latin American countries (Arsel et al., 2016b; Svampa, 2015). Gramsci's concept of hegemony unifies both material and ideological consensus elements of domination by "the sense of everyday reason," which accepts certain central dimensions of power and social domination as unquestionable (Gramsci, 1992). Extractivism is a clear example of hegemony with high political support and economic necessity that gives considerable power to the extractivist discourse, which in turn becomes a political discourse often seen as an unquestionable sense of everyday reason (Acosta & Brand, 2018).

Focusing specifically on narratives, Gudynas's (2019) article "To the Last Drop" explores the narratives sustaining extractivism, shedding light on how these narratives perpetuate hegemonic structures. Despite citizen protests and resistance, extractive practices gather support from various societal sectors, academia, and governments, both conservative and progressive. The article contends that extractive narratives blend factual assertions with moral premises, interpretations with opinions, and often omit or invisibilize certain information. These narratives promote ideas of "zero impact" or "full remediation,"

downplay territorial effects, justify economic necessity, and uphold corporate self-regulation, all while privileging “expert-based sciences” over alternative forms of knowledge (Gudynas, 2019).

Such narratives selectively emphasize specific ideas while marginalizing others, reinforcing political agendas. The pervasive influence of extractivism spans multiple cultural and political dimensions, bolstered by interconnected concepts, institutions, and power resources that work to legitimize and sustain it (Gudynas, 2019). In parallel, Gudynas (2019) highlights the importance of deconstructing these narratives and advocating for counter-narratives that expose the adverse impacts of extractivism and pave the way for the emergence of post-extractive alternatives.

4.3 Post-Extractivism

Critiques of extractivism and its socio-environmental impacts have increasingly called for alternatives to the current political and economic model, with post-extractivism emerging as part of these conversations (Acosta, 2017, 2017; Acosta & Brand, 2018; Gudynas, 2011a; Svampa, 2012). Broadly, post-extractivism proposes transitioning societies away from dependence on extractivist practices and growth-driven economic models toward sustainable, regenerative, and equitable systems that emphasize ecological sustainability, local autonomy, and economic models prioritizing well-being (Acosta, 2017; Gudynas, 2011a).

Gudynas (2011a, p. 63) claims that the core of post-extractivism lies in questioning, *“How can we begin to walk the path that will free us from extractivist dependence?”* Moreover, it argues that these transitions do not imply a complete ban on natural resource extraction; instead, they seek alternatives to conventional extractivism, characterized by its intense impacts and reliance on core economies tied to globalization and transnational networks. Therefore, post-extractivism represents a *“rejection of the submissive acceptance of extractivism and an effort to explore possible alternatives”* (Gudynas, 2011a, p. 63). However, the article recognizes that conventional development is still firmly in place and insists on defending economic growth as the engine of progress while at the same time minimizing and ignoring social and environmental impacts (Gudynas, 2011a).

This recognition of the hegemonic power of extractivism is a fundamental element of the discussions around post-extractivism (Acosta & Brand, 2018; Gudynas, 2011a; Svampa, 2012). Scholars argue that the hegemonic nature of extractivism has promoted the extractivist model to become incrustated in all aspects of modern living, politics, the economy, and the interaction with nature. Therefore, this element often appears in connection to the concepts of commodity consensus (Svampa, 2015) and imperial mode of

living (Brand & Wissen, 2012), which allude to systems linked to extractivism either in its political-economic nature or at the social level. As Acosta & Brand (2018, p. 26) put it,

"If Fordism contributed to lay the cultural foundations of what could be defined as an imperial way of life, extractivism, with its centuries-old roots in Latin America, has become so entrenched that we could say - figuratively speaking - that in its societies, starting with its elites, there is a sort of 'extractivist DNA.'"

Consequently, scholars propose broader societal transformations and restructuring of economic models as ways of departing from extractivism, arguing that small changes do not alter the current model (Acosta & Brand, 2018; Svampa, 2015). For example, during the *commodities consensus*, the social advancements achieved have proven insufficient and unsustainable, as they failed to challenge the colonial roots of neo-extractivism and capitalism (Svampa, 2015). This was evident in countries with progressive governments like Venezuela, Ecuador, Brazil, and Bolivia, where extractivism persisted and even expanded under such regimes (Svampa, 2015).

Academic discussions around post-extractivism call for societal transformations, taking a critical position towards the idea(s) of development and economic growth, which are the frameworks to which the extractive model responds. While a singular definition of post-extractivism was not found, the discussions around it are closely tied to broader debates on post-development, *Buen Vivir*, and critiques of neo-developmentalism, the imperial mode of living, neoextractivism, the commodity consensus, and perpetual economic growth under capitalism (Acosta & Brand, 2018; Brand & Wissen, 2012; Svampa, 2012). This linkage to other debates helps position the discussions on post-extractivism in clear theoretical areas.

4.3.1 Positioning Post-Extractivism: Theoretical Foundations and Intersections

Post-extractivism is not a stand-alone concept; it emerges within and alongside broader theoretical frameworks that critique dominant development and resource exploitation models. It is deeply intertwined with post-development debates and resonates with discussions on degrowth, the eco-territorial turn, epistemologies of the South, and the concept of *Buen Vivir*. This section situates post-extractivism within these intersecting discourses, highlighting its theoretical foundations and the key perspectives that shape its position.

Post-development is a critical perspective that challenges the dominant discourse of development, rooted in modernity and tied to colonial and capitalist frameworks (Svampa, 2012). Coined by Arturo Escobar, it aims to dismantle the structures of power, myths, and imaginaries that sustain conventional development

models (Escobar, 2015). With this, post-development critiques the dichotomy between development and underdevelopment, the institutionalization of development, and the marginalization of local knowledge and practices (Svampa, 2015; Unceta, 2018).

This concept started to position itself in the 1980s in Latin America, when a number of critical views began to appear, openly questioning the capacity of economic growth to overcome underdevelopment and generate development - understood as an increase in people's well-being (Unceta, 2018). Discussions also gained space after the publication of the Meadows report "The Limits to Growth" (1972). As a result, the ecological perspective challenged the dominant developmentalism model, signalling to countries in the Global South that the industrial development path taken by the Global North "*was far from being a universal blueprint*" (Svampa, 2012, p. 56). Post-development calls, therefore, for alternative approaches grounded in decoloniality, ecological sustainability, and respect for Indigenous worldviews, emphasizing the need for a different valuation of nature and a rethinking of the relationship between humans and the environment (Gudynas, 2011a; Svampa, 2012).

Within the post-development discourse, extractivism is a concept that highlights the exploitation of natural resources and its role in deepening inequalities between the Global North and South while also contributing to human rights violations, such as the suppression of Indigenous rights and the criminalization of social protests. Svampa (2012) presents the extractive model as a central concept for understanding interconnected crises, such as the ecological crisis, global economic imbalances, and the challenges of financial capitalism. Post-extractivism arises from post-development debates as an alternative framework and a response to the extractive economic model.

The critique of the extractive model and its intrinsic connection to crises of capitalism is also taken by academics like Acosta and Brand (2018), who propose degrowth and post-extractivism as interlinked ways out of the "*capitalist maze*." On the one hand, degrowth is a collective and deliberate process aimed at reducing production and consumption and is directed predominantly toward industrialized societies. The goal of degrowth is to bring ecological sustainability, social equity, and improved quality of life to the centre of attention by moving the focus beyond the pursuit of economic growth (Hickel, 2021; Schneider et al., 2011). On the other hand, the main goal of post-extractivism is to consider alternatives to the current development model and dependency on extractivist practices, taking into account the inequalities and impacts created by the current production model (Acosta & Brand, 2018). Acosta (2017) argues that in the face of social, environmental, and financial crises, economic growth—especially in the Global North—must be halted or reversed for sustainability. In a finite world, perpetual growth drives ecological

and social instability. Degrowth aligns with post-extractivism, as reduced demand for raw materials in the North would push Southern economies to shift from export dependence toward self-sufficiency (Acosta, 2017).

Both these frameworks call for a radical restructuring of current economic systems that prioritize profit and growth at the expense of the ecological and social spheres. This way, scholars emphasize the importance of combining global North and South perspectives to look beyond capitalism, focusing on ecological sustainability, social justice, and alternative forms of living and governance (Acosta & Brand, 2018). Acosta and Brandt (2018) recognize that the concepts are two combinable parts of a transition from capitalism. Degrowth and post-extractivism emphasize redistributing wealth, income, power, and agency and critique modernist, capitalist, and predominantly Western economic models. Both concepts reject “false alternatives” rooted in immediate solutions to complex realities that require profound structural societal transformation (Acosta & Brand, 2018). Hence, degrowth and post-extractivism advocate for a socio-ecological transformation encompassing economic, political, cultural, and ethical dimensions. These approaches emphasize that meaningful alternatives to capitalism require collective action, cultural shifts, and deep ecological awareness, challenging the dominant narratives of progress and development (Acosta & Brand, 2018).

Post-extractivism intersects with broader theoretical debates and is connected to key concepts within academic discussions. Next, I highlight three particularly relevant concepts to this thesis: *epistemologies of the South*, as a decolonial perspective; the *eco-territorial turn*, which links extractivism to territorial struggles; and *Buen Vivir*, a framework for reimagining ways of life, often considered the goal of post-extractivist and social-ecological transformations.

First, in the post-extractivism debates, in addition to critiquing instrumental and imperial European rationality, there is a demand to decolonize knowledge and its systems (Acosta & Brand, 2018). This demand is connected to the so-called *epistemologies of the South* (by Sousa Santos, 2011) that seek to show how, implicitly, European thought considers much of the world as “disordered” and that it must be exploited, repressed, and finally, integrated into the European vision. Epistemologies of the South propose the expansion of the political imagination beyond the intellectual and political exhaustion of the global North (Sousa Santos, 2011). In this way, it calls to expand the possibilities and rethink the world from the knowledge and practices of the Global South, starting from epistemology, language, and epistemic subordination (Sousa Santos, 2011), requesting for different forms of knowledge to be appreciated as equal, to turn them into elements of decolonization (Acosta & Brand, 2018).

Second, scholars such as Marisella Svampa (2015) recognize that today's struggles revolve around concrete territories, especially in Latin America. She introduced the term *eco-territorial turn* to emphasize that current social struggles are primarily about land and territories. Explaining how, for certain forms of life, cosmovision and subsistence, this, in turn, means struggles for more autonomy and self-determination (Svampa, 2015). The eco-territorial turn is a term that connects territorialities with struggles against social marginalization, the destruction of the environment, and the valorisation of human beings and nature (Svampa, 2015).

Third and last, proposed alternative models are commonly connected to the *Buen Vivir* or *Sumak Kawsay* or *Suma Qamaña* (good life for all) as an emancipatory concept to rethink ways of life. There are several lines of discussion on the use of *Buen Vivir*. Here, I use the definition by Acosta (2017), which presents a concept that emphasizes living in harmony with nature and within a community, prioritizing collective well-being over individual consumption. *Buen Vivir* is rooted in *Indigenous* practices and cosmovision, particularly in Latin America. It critiques the Western development model, advocating for ecologically sustainable, culturally enriching, and socially equitable alternative ways of life. *Buen Vivir* challenges the capitalist notion of progress and growth, offering a vision of development that respects natural limits and values human dignity and community solidarity (Acosta, 2017). In other words,

“This conception of life, where relationality plays a preponderant role, will require an incessant and complex flow of interactions and exchanges. Giving and receiving, through a never-ending process of reciprocities, complementarities, and solidarities, constitutes the basis for Buen Vivir. This means we must assume an ethical stance that should govern human lives: take care of yourself and other living beings. In this world of harmonies, life takes precedence over any other consideration. We would say, in terms of political confrontation, that Buen Vivir is concerned with reproducing life and not capital.” (Acosta, 2017, para. 77)

Moreover, Acosta (2017) argues that *Buen Vivir* is rooted in utopian visions, manifesting within the existing capitalist system in various ways, drawing on the pressing need to foster harmony among people, society, and nature. This approach emphasizes self-sufficiency and self-management at the heart of a community life. In the past decades, *Buen Vivir* has become an important concept in post-extractivism and anti-capitalist movements in Latin America, especially in countries like Bolivia and Ecuador (Arsel et al., 2016b). It was institutionalized in Ecuador's Constitution in 2008 as a guiding principle for sustainable development and governance, along with recognizing a plurinational state and the Rights of Nature (Asamblea Nacional, 2008).

5 Case Contextualization

This study focuses on the **Ecuadorian referendum held on August 20, 2023, which sought to ban oil exploitation in the ITT Block (Block 43) of Yasuni National Park**. The 2023 Yasuní referendum emerges from a complex set of factors and extensive history, stretching far beyond the immediate context of the vote itself. This referendum was born from a long, multifaceted history of social movements in Ecuador, influenced by broader political, economic, and historical dynamics. Together, these elements reveal the context of the referendum and the significance of the struggle to preserve the Yasuní region. This section provides essential background to situate the case within its broader historical, social, and ecological framework. Understanding this case requires not only familiarity with the specific characteristics of the ITT block but also an appreciation for its broader context. The writing of this section was informed and adapted from the results of the data analysis.

5.1 National Context

The Republic of Ecuador is a sovereign country located in the northwestern region of South America, comprising twenty-four provinces. It is neighbouring Colombia in the north, Peru in the south and east, and the Pacific Ocean in the west. Ecuador has many geographical zones, including Andean peaks, tropical rainforests -known as *Amazonia* because it belongs to the Amazon basin- a coastal region and the volcanic Galapagos Islands. The region of Ecuador was a Spanish colony until 1822 when it became an independent republic. A complex legacy of Indigenous and colonial past makes Ecuador a patchwork of ethnic identities. Its population is 77.5% Mestizo, 7.7% Montubio, 7.7% Indigenous, 2.2% White, 2%, Afro-Ecuadorian, 1.4% Mulatto, 1.3% Black, and 0.1% other (INEC, 2022). The country's economy is highly informal and dependent on the export of raw materials. The country is a world oil exporter, the world's leading exporter of bananas, and a major exporter of flowers, shrimp, and cocoa (World Bank Group, n.a). The following section focuses on contextualizing extractivism in Ecuador and the country's current situation.

5.1.1 Extractivism in Ecuador

Like most Latin American countries, Ecuador has a long history of extractivism, which started in the 15th century when Ecuador was part of the areas colonized by Spain. A period in which Latin America played an important role in the production of raw materials that would be taken to Europe (Acosta, 2001). This happened under models of racialization with forced labour, slavery, appropriation of territories, and use

of power structures. Leaving traces of social division and the first debts that the country would have, which also created a need for the continuation of raw material extraction for export (Acosta, 2001).

Initially, Ecuador joined international markets with products like cacao, coffee, banana, and shrimp, but a new player soon arrived at the scene: hydrocarbons. After the discovery of the first oil deposit in 1911, the search for crude oil reserves expanded into the Ecuadorian Amazon Region (Acosta, 2001). By the 1930s, several mining and oil concessions had been signed, especially with international companies (Acosta, 2001). By the 1960s, the country began exporting oil, quickly becoming a significant revenue source. This led to a so-called "oil boom" in 1972 that shifted the economy's focus towards the extractive sector, which started to be considered the country's primary driver of economic growth (Acosta, 2001; Larrea, 2024).

The "oil boom" brought several promises of economic development. And in fact, it led Ecuador to a level of economic growth that had not been seen before. However, since it did not correspond to a similar qualitative transformation for the population, it soon crystallized into the myth of development or resource curse (Acosta, 2001; Ross, 1999). Despite substantial oil revenues, the country has struggled with persistent social inequality, political instability, and a lack of economic diversification, impeding sustainable development (León, 2017; Swallow, 2017). The hopes for the country to become a prosperous, equitable and diversified society have not yet materialized after fifty-two years of oil extraction. Not only is one-third of the population affected by poverty, and underemployment affects almost half of the labour force (Larrea et al., 2024), but the economy continues to depend on less than a dozen primary products (Larrea, 2024).

As a result, the Ecuadorian economy relies heavily on international oil prices, and its possibilities for productive diversification, economic growth, and social development projects depend on them. After half a century of oil exports, the growth achieved has been low and unstable, following the volatile fluctuations of international oil prices (Larrea, 2024). The country had two periods of "oil boom" when the international price was good between 1972 and 1982 and 2004 and 2014 (Tenecota Quezada et al., 2024). In these times, the country had higher purchasing and borrowing power, which connected these boom periods with increases in loan-based project financing. During the remaining intervals, a low or declining export purchasing power prevailed, generating several economic and social crises (Swallow, 2017). However, the illusion of wealth connected to oil extraction prevails, and governments that take power have typically committed to the discourse that the country needs to increase exploitation to fund development projects (Arsel et al., 2016a).

Ecuador offers an illustrative example of several concepts discussed in the theoretical framework, such as the extractivist model (Gudynas, 2019), the extractive imperative (Arsel et al., 2016a; Swallow, 2017), resource curse (Ross, 1999), and neo-extractivism (Acosta, 2013). Over decades of neoliberalism focused on oil extraction, the country experienced substantial economic revenue, but it also saw increasing corruption and recurring economic crises, including the severe 1998 crisis that led to dollarization in 2000 (Acosta, 2001; Riofrancos, 2017). These dynamics manifest aspects of the resource curse and the extractivist model (Ross, 1999). This period unified social movements in resisting austerity and reclaiming national sovereignty. However, the rise of the left did not signify a departure from the extractivist framework (Riofrancos, 2017).

Rafael Correa (modern leftist) was elected president in 2006 on the promise to represent “the change of an era” and the departure of neoliberal systems. During his election, he managed a nationalist, sentimental and environmentalist discourse and proceeded to grant nature rights in the new constitution, which includes the “*Sumak Kawsay*” (Buen Vivir-Good life for all) (Asamblea Nacional, 2008; Goeury, 2021). Correa introduced numerous programs to address poverty, inequality, and environmental protection, including the Yasuní-ITT initiative. Nevertheless, Ecuador continued to depend heavily on extractive industries and international loans to fund public services.

Under Correa’s administration, rising oil prices led to a period of political stability and economic growth (Swallow, 2017), with more oil fields opened than ever before, deepening Ecuador’s reliance on oil and international lending (Goeury, 2021). This extractivist approach persisted in the administrations that followed—Lenin Moreno, Guillermo Lasso, and Daniel Noboa—across political lines, illustrating the reinforcement of the extractive imperative (Swallow, 2017) and neoliberal policies (Acosta, 2013).

Extractivism in Ecuador has evolved through various phases but maintains a consistent structural reliance on resource extraction regardless of the government in power (Riofrancos, 2017). Therefore, the pro-extractivist stance can be considered hegemonic, especially considering the state’s significant role in managing oil resources, the constant and central place of oil revenues in the national discourse, and the historical emphasis on the “oil boom” as a pillar of the economy, with a limited critique of the underlying social and environmental impacts. Meanwhile, anti-extractivist counter-narratives are primarily sustained by social movements.

5.1.2 Current Situation in the Country

The case study is embedded into current events and dynamics that impact the country. A complex interplay of dependency on extractive industries, political instability, social unrest, and the effects of climate change shapes Ecuador's economic and political landscape. The political landscape has been marked by frequent turnover and significant opposition in recent years. At the same time, economic challenges stem from debt obligations, limited diversification, challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic, and high levels of social inequality. Social unrest has sparked on several occasions in connection with economic difficulties, drug-related violence, and climate crisis impacts (InSight Crime, 2024; Meriguet, 2024; World Bank Group, n.a).

Following President Rafael Correa's leftist administration (2007–2017), which ended with several corruption scandals that drew him out of the country, his successor, Lenin Moreno, initially pursued Correa's policies but eventually shifted towards neoliberal reforms. Guillermo Lasso, a conservative banker elected in 2021, promised economic stability but struggled with corruption scandals, declining public approval, and rising opposition over fuel subsidies and tax reforms. Lasso's administration ended prematurely in May 2023 when he dissolved the National Assembly to avoid impeachment over alleged fraud in public contracts. He triggered early elections by invoking the constitutional "*muerte cruzada*" (mutual death) mechanism, resulting in a shortened term (Silva, 2024). In August 2023, general elections and a national referendum on oil exploitation in Yasuni National Park (alongside a local referendum on mining in Choco Andino) took place (CNE, 2023a). The election brought Daniel Noboa to the presidency, whose administration focuses on enhancing public safety and addressing Ecuador's energy crisis with a centrist neoliberal approach, which has also faced corruption scandals and social unrest (Silva, 2024). The next presidential elections are scheduled for spring 2025.

Ecuador faces significant economic pressures, including a fiscal deficit of at least \$5.7 billion and a growing external debt totalling \$47.5 billion, limiting Ecuador's borrowing options to institutions like the International Monetary Fund and other multilateral organizations (Larrea, 2024). Many of these loans come with conditions, such as austerity measures, that require cuts to public spending. The economic fallout from COVID-19 and recent geopolitical changes have further influenced global markets and crude oil prices, impacting Ecuador's economy (Riofrancos, 2017).

In addition, Ecuadorians have experienced rising inflation, which has driven up costs for food, fuel, and essential goods. This inflation hits low-income and rural populations hardest, worsening economic

inequality. These pressures have fuelled social unrest in recent years. For example, in 2022, widespread protests erupted as citizens demanded solutions for the rising cost of living, reform of fuel subsidies, and consultation with Indigenous communities on land extraction issues (Espinoza, 2024).

Security in Ecuador has deteriorated, with drug trafficking-related violence becoming a critical and escalating issue. At the beginning of 2024, the government declared an internal armed conflict as violence intensified, affecting public safety and compounding national instability (InSight Crime, 2024)

Ecuador is also heavily impacted by the climate crisis. The country is, for example, facing a prolonged drought from El Niño and climate change. In 2024, Ecuador faced an energy crisis largely due to reduced hydroelectric output that usually generates 80% of the country's electricity, outdated infrastructure, and its dependency on imported energy during shortages. The country faced planned energy blackouts for most of 2024, which lasted up to 14 hours a day in October (Meriguet, 2024). This energy disruption has strained daily life, created pressure on industries, increased unemployment, and affected food and housing prices, further deepening the economic crisis. Climate-related challenges have highlighted Ecuador's vulnerability to climate change, worsening the complex socio-economic landscape.

5.2 Local Context

This section shifts the focus to a more localized perspective, beginning with exploring Yasuní National Park. It examines the park's unique ecological and social dynamics, highlighting the interactions between local communities, and the impacts of oil extraction. By doing so, this discussion situates the case study within its immediate geographical and socio-environmental context.

5.2.1 The Yasuni National Park

The Yasuni National Park, established as a national park in 1979, is located in the Ecuadorian Amazon across the provinces of Orellana and Pastaza (Figure 2). Scientific studies have identified the Yasuni region as the most biodiverse area on the planet, hosting the greatest diversity of amphibians, birds, mammals, insects, and plants per square meter, as shown in Figure 3 below (Bass et al., 2010; Finer et al., 2009; Mittermeier & Goettsch Mittermeier, 1997). This exceptional biodiversity also led UNESCO to declare it a Biosphere Reserve in 1989 (UNESCO, 1989).

Figure 2: Map of the Yasuni Region (GRID-Arendal, 2013)

Figure 3: Species richness patterns of northern South America. (Bass et al., 2010, p. 3)

Species richness for A) amphibians, B) birds, C) mammals, and D) vascular plants

The Yasuni National Park is also home to various Indigenous groups and nationalities, including two groups, the Tagaeri and Taromenane, who live in voluntary isolation. As a recognition of the need to protect these communities, the Ecuadorian government created the *Zona Intangible Tagaeri Taromenane*

(ZITT) or “untouchable zone” in 1999, and in 2007, designated the southern area of Yasuni to safeguard the territories of Indigenous peoples living in isolation (Decreto N° 552 - 1999). However, experts argue that the ZITT does not encompass the entirety of these Indigenous territories, as several oil blocks overlap with areas crucial for their survival, leading to significant territorial pressures, conflicts, and even fatalities (Narváez, 2021).

5.2.2 Territorial and Social Dynamics

While the Yasuní-ITT discussion has reached national and international levels, the debate around the case should remain rooted in local history, inhabitants, and struggles. Despite its global relevance, understanding the Yasuní referendum requires grounding it in the complex, longstanding issues faced by local communities.

In Ecuador, oil extraction projects have been primarily concentrated in the eastern region, particularly in the central-northern Amazon. This territory has been the homeland of various Indigenous groups for centuries. Historically, the Waorani and their relatives, the Tagaeri, have inhabited this region (Rival, 1994), with the inclusion of more recent populations, including the Taromenane, Kichwa, Shuar, and *colonos*³ in the last decades (Martínez, 2009). The expansion of extractive activities, especially oil and gas, has led to intensified processes of contact, colonization, and gradual land dispossession for Indigenous communities (Narváez, 2021). These processes are enabled by actors such as oil companies and the state, which have promoted extractive control over Indigenous territories through governance, territorial appropriation, and infrastructure development. The legislation further empowers the state to claim ownership over oil resources, granting it authority also to make territorial decisions and assert material control over lands with raw materials (León, 2017).

Anthropologists describe the Waorani as a semi-nomadic hunter-gatherer group originally divided into four distinct clans within the Yasuní region (Rival, 1994). Their subsistence practices traditionally involve a mix of forest resource gathering, hunting, cultivation of small gardens (*chacras* or *kewenas*), and trade (Narváez, 2021). Mobility is a defining feature of Waorani territoriality in Yasuní. Their movement is

³ In Ecuador, name given to settlers, generally, colonos provide their labour in exchange for either access to land or for a portion of the harvest.

structured around short-term, stationary periods where they settle in an area for hunting and gathering, as well as long-term, cyclic shifts tied to uxori-local⁴ marriage alliance (Narváez, 2021).

The Waorani have historically defended their homeland with vigour, perceiving outside interferences as threats. This defensive attitude was illustrated in deadly attacks against Royal–Dutch–Shell workers in the 1930s, incidents that marked early encounters with the company's oil exploration efforts (Finer et al., 2009). Confrontations that continued to happen contributed to an external narrative framing the Waorani as "savages" in need of "pacification." The 1970s brought further disruption through forced displacement linked to oil extraction activities, which reportedly contributed to the disappearance of groups such as the Tetetes (Franco, 2006).

The start of oil exploitation was also accompanied by Evangelical missionaries, notably the Summer Institute of Linguistics (SIL), which significantly altered Waorani settlement patterns in the 1950s. SIL's evangelization campaign forcibly contracted about 80% of the Waorani population into less than 10% of their ancestral lands, resulting in significant cultural and spatial displacement (Trujillo, 2011). The efforts of SIL led to forced cultural contact and transformation with strong external influences that reshaped traditional practices and ways of life (Franco, 2006). Only the Tagaeri clan, one of the four Waorani clans, managed to evade this process by retreating into remote areas of Yasuní (Trujillo, 2011).

In the early 1970s, as SIL's influence declined and local forest resources deteriorated, many Waorani returned to what they regarded as their rightful territories, only to encounter *colonos* who had begun arriving following the construction of the Auca Road by Texaco in 1967 (Finer et al., 2009). This influx sparked immediate tensions over land use and resource access. In response, the Waorani established the Organization of Waorani Nationalities of Ecuador, now known as Waorani Nationality Ecuador (NAWE), to advocate for their land rights and cultural autonomy. NAWE later joined both the Confederation of Indigenous Nationalities of the Ecuadorian Amazon (CONFENIAE) and the National Confederation of Indigenous Nationalities of Ecuador (CONAIE) to strengthen their position further and coordinate efforts across Indigenous groups in the country (Espinosa, 2013). The NAWE advocated officially recognising Waorani land rights, petitioning the government to grant them legal title to portions of their ancestral territory (Rival, 1994).

⁴ In social anthropology, uxori-local residence is the societal system in which a married couple resides with or near the wife's parents.

For the Waorani, as for many Indigenous Amazonian groups, preserving their cultural identity is intrinsically tied to their ability to maintain access to their lands. In the past decade, the Yasuní region has remained a focal point for oil frontier expansion, leading to repeated conflicts involving Indigenous groups, often disrupted by oil and logging industries that disturb traditional land-use patterns and mobility (Narváez, 2021). The arbitrary borders established by the state, whether they are the boundaries of oil blocks or intangible zones, are unrealistic in the practical understanding of both the Waorani and Indigenous peoples living in voluntary isolation, so their implementation is practically pointless for those impacted by the oil industry (Narváez, 2021).

Under current conditions, state action maintains colonial and monocultural notions that do not consider the cultural diversity in the Amazonian Region (Narváez, 2021). Indigenous peoples are the most affected group by oil exploitation in the Amazon region, as extractivism has created a pattern of colonization, settlement, and loss of their territory and culture. Extractive industries' invasion has also generated significant social, cultural, economic and environmental impacts, now posing existential threats to the isolated Indigenous populations within Yasuní (Finer et al., 2009; León, 2017; Narváez, 2021).

5.2.3 Impacts of Oil Extraction

Now, this sub-section will focus on the impacts of the oil industry after having examined the social dynamics within Yasuni National Park. This discussion is crucial, as understanding the local-level consequences of oil extractivism provides an essential context for analysing post-extractivist transformations, which is at the core of this study.

Oil extraction of the ITT block started in 2016, and since then, the local environment and communities have been affected by direct and indirect impacts of oil extraction. Effects can be recognized immediately in the short, medium, and long term. They affect the environmental, political, economic, cultural and social areas and have been increasingly documented in academic literature, especially in blocks close to the ITT that have been active for a longer period of time (e.g., Codato et al., 2022; Dominguez-Gaibor et al., 2023; Eugenio et al., 2024; Freire & Bayón, 2022; Soliz Torres et al., 2023, etc.). The mentioned characteristics of oil extraction impacts have made it challenging to have a clear and complete overview, as they are manifold, interconnected, and complex to measure.

Eugenio et al. (2024), for instance, carried out a Life-Cycle Assessment qualifying the footprints associated with the extraction, transportation, refining, distribution and final uses of the oil in four different scenarios (oil for asphalt use, electricity, marine fuel and passenger car transport). This study complements the Life-

Cycle Assessment findings with a qualitative analysis of the social, cultural and environmental implications of oil extraction for Waorani communities. Eugenio et al. (2024) conclude that the extraction process's environmental burdens in blocks 16 and 67 in 2015 were greater than those of major oil-producing nations - such as the United States, Saudi Arabia and Indonesia- based on analysing 11⁵ impact categories. Moreover, an increase of 139.01 % over 24 years of carbon emissions from extraction was detected in the studied block. Based on the qualitative analysis, it was determined that the primary local effects are linked to challenges in environmental monitoring and information access, the economic reliance of local communities on the oil extraction company, and cultural shifts; table 3 presents an overview of documented local impacts of oil exploitation based on Eugenio et al. (2024) and includes other findings from other articles.

Table 3: Overview of impacts produced directly and indirectly by oil exploitation (Alianza de Derechos Humanos de Ecuador, 2023; Eugenio et al., 2024; Finer et al., 2009; Freire & Bayón, 2022; Soliz Torres et al., 2023; Y. M. Suárez et al., 2019)

Impact Category	Impacts	
Environmental	Oils spills	Land degradation and land use shifts
	Pollution due to reinjection of formation waters	Decrease in environmental protection in protected areas
	Deforestation	Forest edge effects
	Noises and waste	Disrupted hydrology, loss of fish habitats
	Air and water pollution	Overhunting and illegal logging
	Habitat fragmentation	Habitat fragmentation
	Soil erosion	Vehicle-wildlife collisions
	Invasive species	
Social	Alcoholism and Drug addiction	Consumption of polluted water
	Health problems	Little or no access to basic services
	Violence and thefts	Racism
	Problems of mental health	Prostitution
	Poor living conditions	Gender inequalities and violence
	Inter-family problems	Insufficient introduction to education
Cultural	Territorial dispossession	Abandonment of semi-nomadic lifestyle
	Abandonment of traditional indigenous economic activities and disengagement with the territory	Territorial disputes of contacted and uncontacted indigenous groups
	Changes in cultural habits and identity transformations	In-migration / Arrival of settlers
	Conflicts among indigenous groups/communities	Loss of unity and conflicts within communities

⁵ Terrestrial Acidification Potential (TAP), Global Warming Potential (GWP), Terrestrial Ecotoxicity Potential (TEP), Abiotic Depletion Potential on Fossil Fuels (ADP-FF), Freshwater Eutrophication Potential (FEP), Human Carcinogenic Toxicity Potential (HTPc), Water Consumption Potential (WCP), Ecosystem Quality Loss Potential (EQL), Human Health Reduction (HHR), Effects on Natural Resources (ENR) and Energy Footprint (EF).

	Difficulty in domestic activities such as bathing, washing, drinking water, food preparation and transport due to contaminated water.	Destruction of places of spiritual value to native peoples, such as lakes, waterfalls, rocks and salt pans.
Political	Lack of environmental monitoring, information and transparency Lack of social monitoring Lack of participation Lack of responsibility and ethics	Limitation of movement and information (fenced block) Lack of land ownership (titles) Loss of stataal sovereignty Clientelism and corruption
Economic	Dependence on the company but without investment in further economic development Dependence on money and abandonment of indigenous economic practices Departure from the area by the company without transition/compensation	Territorial dispossession and unequal distribution of oil benefits Lack of financial compensation for pollution

Many of these impacts are interconnected or arise indirectly from one another. A crucial aspect of understanding the effects of oil extraction lies in identifying the processes of environmental damage and cultural transformation that follow road construction. Finer et al. (2009) elaborate on how, despite being promoted as a "low impact" road, the Maxus Road⁶ has led to significant direct and even more substantial indirect impacts. Direct impacts include habitat fragmentation, soil erosion, disrupted hydrology, vehicle-wildlife collisions, and forest edge effects. Indirect impacts involve deforestation and overhunting caused by the colonization of the road by Kichwa and Waorani communities, which face lifestyle changes due to the presence of oil companies in their territories and new infrastructure access (Finer et al., 2009; Suárez et al., 2009). Road access also leads to increases in illegal logging and hunting (Suárez et al., 2019).

The construction of the Maxus Road and other oil extraction infrastructure within the Yasuní National Park and the Waorani Ethnic Reserve prompted several Waorani clans to abandon their semi-nomadic way of life and establish permanent settlements along the road (Suárez et al., 2019). This shift led to significant changes in their subsistence practices, including increased access to firearms, road networks, and subsidies provided by oil companies. As a result, hunting transitioned from being solely for subsistence to becoming market-oriented (Suárez et al., 2019).

On another note, a clear increase in health problems has been documented since the arrival of the oil companies to the Amazon region (Alianza de Derechos Humanos de Ecuador, 2023; Almeida & Proaño, 2008; Soliz Torres et al., 2023). A report published by Soliz Torres et al. (2023) highlights the considerable

⁶ One of the roads opened in the Yasuni National Park

impacts on health, especially for children and women in indigenous communities, produced by impacts on the environmental and social changes produced by the oil extraction industry.

Impacts on health arise primarily due to the consumption of contaminated water and poor access to basic services, especially the health care system (Soliz Torres et al., 2023). Water is essential for daily activities, including personal hygiene, drinking (for humans and animals), food preparation, crop irrigation, and recreation. However, oil extraction and colonisation activities have impacted most water sources in the Ecuadorian Amazon Region. As a result, people often consume contaminated water, either due to a lack of awareness of contamination or a lack of alternatives (Soliz Torres et al., 2023).

In order of frequency of recurrence, the health impacts connected to oil exploitation and consequent environmental pollution are: Cancer, Disabilities, Skin problems, Digestive system problems, Sexually transmitted infections, Malnutrition, Infant mortality, and Neurological problems, among several others (Alianza de Derechos Humanos de Ecuador, 2023; Soliz Torres et al., 2023). In 2013, the rate of cancer-related deaths in oil-extracting regions was three times higher than the national average (Acosta, 2013). The lack of medical care, pharmaceutical supplies, and care at health centres has further contributed to the increase in cancer mortality rates in the Amazon Region (Soliz Torres et al., 2023).

Academic studies and reports have also demonstrated a clear gender dimension in the impacts of oil exploitation. Health issues disproportionately affect female bodies, as they often come into direct contact with contaminated water through household responsibilities (Gálvez Mancilla et al., 2021; Soliz Torres et al., 2023). Additionally, other gendered impacts have been identified, including sexual harassment and violence, unequal access to work and education, gender gaps in education, employment, and political participation, as well as complications during pregnancy and childbirth, congenital malformations, miscarriages, and abortions (Soliz Torres et al., 2023).

Likewise, the influence of evangelisation and the oil industry has changed the dynamics between genders in this region. In the past, Waorani maintained a social system that promoted equality and equitable distribution of labour (Almeida & Proaño, 2008). In contrast, the introduction of oil extractive projects in the Amazonian region of Ecuador, together with the presence of the SIL and settlers, has consolidated patriarchal structures. This phenomenon has led to increasingly unequal and violent gender relations (Freire & Bayón, 2022). Tapia (2022) further states that communities located within the influence zones of extractive activities experience higher rates of sexual violence and trafficking of women and girls compared to those outside these zones. Similarly, Almeida and Proaño (2008) point out that in all oil fields

investigated, cases of sexual harassment of women by company workers were disclosed. Indigenous populations are the main ones affected, as the opening of oil blocks in their territories destroys their way of life and turns them into focal points of disease and sexual abuse (Gálvez Mancilla et al., 2021).

This provides a broader context for understanding what oil extraction has meant in Yasuni, beyond its environmental implications. Additionally, it connects to the previously discussed impacts on the economy and social inequality, highlighting the far-reaching consequences of extractivism in the region.

5.3 The Road to the 2023 Yasuni Referendum

After outlining the national and local contexts, I now turn to the history of the Yasuní referendum, which is the focus of this thesis. This section examines the Yasuní-ITT initiative, its trajectory toward a popular referendum, and the key social groups engaged in the process. Additionally, I explore the decline of oil in the ITT block.

The ITT Initiative, named after the Ishpingo-Tambococha-Tiputini (ITT) oil fields in block 43 within the Yasuni National Park, was launched by Ecuador's government in 2007 as an innovative proposal to leave the region's oil reserves untapped in exchange for international compensation totalling half the estimated oil revenue, around 3.6 billion US dollars (Larrea & Warnars, 2009). The financial compensation for not exploiting the oil was intended to be invested in renewable energy projects, biodiversity protection, and the conservation of 44 protected areas in the country.

This way, the Yasuni-ITT initiative sought to challenge prevailing mindsets and imaginations by questioning the central role of oil in our capitalist society and the responsibility of the Global North in global climate mitigation. Notably, it urged a re-evaluation of Ecuador's dependency on oil and the environmental and social impacts caused by the industry (Le Quang, 2016). Despite significant global support, the initiative was cancelled in 2013 due to insufficient funding, which has since stirred national and international debate (Finer et al., 2009; Kingsbury et al., 2019; Swallow, 2017).

The same government that initiated this revolutionary initiative was responsible for putting it in the vault and, by 2016, started the exploitation in the ITT block of the Yasuní National Park, showed in Figure 2 (Sovacool & Scarpaci, 2016; Yasunidos, 2021). To date, there are eight oil blocks within Yasuní National Park: 12, 14, 15, 16, 17, 31, 43 (ITT), and 67. In addition, 13 other blocks around it also affect the Yasuní region (Ministerio de Energia y Minas, 2018).

When President Correa announced the end of the Yasuni-ITT initiative, the announcement was justified on three grounds: 1) oil revenues as essential for Ecuador's development; 2) international failure to compensate Ecuador for non-extraction; and 3) a claimed minimal environmental impact on the area, estimated at 1 in 1,000 (Mancilla & Martínez, 2014).

However, this decision was met with opposition from sectors of Ecuadorian society, sparking the creation of the YASunidos Collective on August 18, 2013 (Yasunidos, 2021). Their arguments emphasized Yasuni's unparalleled biodiversity, the presence of indigenous communities in voluntary isolation, longstanding concerns over corruption and oil spills, and the principle that "life is worth more than oil and money" (Mancilla & Martínez, 2014). The unilateral decision to begin oil extraction was seen as a violation of constitutional principles, including the rights of nature (Art. 71), the prohibition of extracting oil in protected areas (Art. 407), and the protection of Indigenous territories (Art. 57) (Asamblea Nacional, 2008; Mancilla & Martínez, 2014).

When public protests were violently suppressed, YASunidos shifted strategies, initiating national debate and collecting signatures to call for a national referendum, challenging and questioning the official stance (Mancilla & Martínez, 2014). In March 2014, YASunidos submitted approximately 480,000 signatures to the National Electoral Council. However, the Council's validation process raised significant concerns about transparency, including issues like breaking the chain of custody and arresting a YASunidos activist (Brito, 2020; Sarmiento, 2021). Ultimately, 239,342 signatures were invalidated, effectively blocking the possibility of a referendum (Brito, 2020). Despite this setback and the commencement of oil operations in Yasuni, YASunidos persisted with its advocacy efforts. Following numerous legal appeals to demonstrate the unconstitutionality of the 2013 process. In September 2022, the Constitutional Court recognized that the rights of YASunidos and petition signatories had been violated. The recognition of unconstitutionality led the National Electoral Council to authorize a national people's referendum to decide if the ITT block should be permanently closed, a milestone achieved after a decade of advocacy (CNE, 2023a; Rosero, 2023).

This recent step brings one to the central point studied in this thesis: the Yasuni referendum. On August 20th, 2023, Ecuador held a national referendum alongside anticipated presidential elections. The ballot posed the question: "**Do you agree that the Ecuadorian government should keep the ITT crude oil,**

known as Block 43, indefinitely underground?" The result was a clear majority in favor, with 58.95%⁷ of Ecuadorians voting "Yes" to close the ITT oil block in Yasuní National Park (CNE, 2023b).

The Yasuni referendum, a first-of-its-kind, marked a significant milestone for environmental and direct democracy, culminating in a notable victory (News Wires, 2023). Over the past decade, Yasuni has gained international recognition, emerging as a symbol of questioning climate responsibility (Le Quang, 2016). This thesis focuses on the narratives surrounding the Yasuni referendum, interpreting the electoral victory as an indication of the growing acceptance of post-extractivist narratives. However, this outcome does not necessarily reflect the broader realities of the environmental movement in Ecuador, which remain complex and multifaceted.

5.3.1 Campaigning for the Yasuni

In the months leading up to the vote, various groups, including the YASunidos Collective, actively campaigned to close the ITT block in the Yasuni National Park. National and local Indigenous and grassroots organizations also actively supported the Yasuní conservation (Machado, 2023). During this time, the principal group name was "Si al Yasuni" (Yes to Yasuni), newly created to include all groups interested in participating and carrying out a simple and unified campaign. The campaign for the Yasuni invited broad public participation, organizing events such as concerts, bike rides, demonstrations, academic panels, and public discussions to raise awareness (Celi, 2023). The slogan "Yes to Yasuní, Yes to Life" became the main message, resonating across Ecuador and drawing support from diverse social groups—a hallmark reminiscent of the protests that began a decade earlier.

Despite the convergence of various causes and social groups in the Yasuni campaign, two prominent actors have played a central role throughout its history: the environmental movement, represented here by YASunidos, and Indigenous groups. I now briefly introduce these two social groups, which embody the unifying struggles that converge in the Yasuni referendum.

YASunidos describes itself as a non-partisan, autonomous, and self-managed social collective (Yasunidos, 2021). A "kaleidoscope" of individuals and viewpoints, the group has taken a stand to "prioritize life over profit." Declaring themselves in a state of ongoing *minga*—or collective effort—YASunidos supports leaving oil underground in Yasuní and embraces efforts that challenge Ecuador's extractive development

⁷ In Ecuador, voting is compulsory for people between 18 and 64 years of age. And it is optional for young people between 16 and 17 years of age, people 65 years of age or older, as well as Ecuadorians living abroad, members of the Armed Forces and National Police on active duty, people with disabilities and illiterate people.

model (Brito, 2020; Yasunidos, 2021). Initially motivated by solidarity and land protection, the collective's struggle grew personal as members faced repression of their rights to protest and participate. Since the Yasuni-ITT Initiative ended, there seems to be no turning back for a population segment unless there is a fundamental change in Ecuador's extractive agenda (Mancilla & Martínez, 2014). Over the past decade, this youth-led movement has evolved significantly, connecting various social groups and aligning with other protests. Though smaller in size now, it has matured as a collective, drawing in older members and a clear picture of their struggles, proposals, and ideals.

The Yasuní cause also has significant support from Ecuador's Indigenous movement, including organizations such as CONAIE, COFENAIE, and NAWA (Machado, 2023). These groups are particularly invested due to the correlation of the ITT block with Indigenous territories. Ecuador's Indigenous movement has a long history of resistance dating back to the colonial era, focusing on land rights, cultural identity, participation rights, protection from mistreatment and abuses, defence of water resources, and preserving their worldview (Muniz et al., 2024). The 2008 Ecuadorian Constitution formally recognized Indigenous rights, establishing Ecuador as a pluralistic state, acknowledging Indigenous justice systems, the *Sumak Kawsay* and recognizing nature as a rights subject (Muniz et al., 2024). The Indigenous struggle has gained international voice and recognition. Here, international allies and Indigenous diplomacy have been a mechanism to “ensure the survival of their cultural wealth in the modern world” (Argudo Pesántez, 2024, p. 34).

5.3.2 Oil Decline in the ITT Block

Addressing Ecuador's declining oil reserves is essential as a final point in contextualizing this case. Ecuador's oil reserves show a downward trend, with models by Espinoza et al. (2019) indicating that peak oil extraction may occur between 2014 and 2025, potentially turning Ecuador into a net oil importer between 2024 and 2035, depending on model and demand scenarios (Espinoza et al., 2019).

This trend includes the ITT block, shown in the graph below, which displays oil extraction in the ITT block from its 2016 start to the present (Larrea, 2024). Extraction volumes have been on a downward trend since peaking at 81,000 barrels per day in 2019, dropping to the current level of 55,000—a 32% decline. The decline has been tempered by production from the *Ishpingo* field, which holds the largest reserves. However, this field also appears to be entering a decline phase. Additionally, one of the reservoirs has an extremely high crude density (8 degrees API), making extraction at profitable prices almost unfeasible (Larrea, 2024). Ecuador's current and future oil dependence would heighten its vulnerability and

compromise energy security and trade balance. Thus, Ecuador must adopt ambitious policies focusing on energy efficiency, renewable energy, and diversifying the production structure (Espinoza et al., 2019)

Figure 4: Oil extraction in ITT-block: 2016-2024 in barrels per day (Larrea, 2024, p. 210)

5.4 State of the Art

This section explores the academic literature and empirical evidence surrounding the Ecuadorian referendum for banning oil exploitation in the Yasuni National Park, specifically focusing on the role of narratives in promoting transformative processes. Given the recent nature of the referendum, limited research directly addresses the themes and questions posed by this study. Still, existing literature offers valuable insights into the broader socio-political and environmental landscape in which the Yasuni referendum unfolded. Four articles published in 2024 were found. These articles focused on the Yasuni-ITT referendum or Initiative, providing information based on different theoretical perspectives. Additionally, the Yasuni-ITT initiative had significant scholarly attention around 2013, providing a foundation of literature that discusses this case in earlier stages. By synthesizing existing literature, this review aims to lay the groundwork for the State of the Art on topics closely related to this thesis.

Mila Maldonado et al. (2024) recently published an article focusing on the mediatic narrative around the Yasuní. This article analyses media framing in the decade from 2013 to 2023 on the Yasuni, focusing on the discourses addressed in newspapers around the oil advance in Yasuní and their impact on the public debate. Researchers recognise a wide range of discussions surrounding Yasuni and that the topic of Yasuni

has been constantly featured in the Ecuadorian media in the past decade (Mila Maldonado et al., 2024). The article seeks to highlight the role of the media and public dialogue. This was done by categorising different arguments by the diverse newspapers where shifting themes according to the government in power were recognized, characterizing the Yasuni as part of state-opposition polarisation debates. Mostly, Yasuni is presented in newspapers with an economic and political focus, while environmental, cultural, social, and territorial issues take a back seat. Similarly, Mila Maldonado et al. (2024) conclude that few sources give space to critical and alternative voices, primarily Indigenous and scientific ones, which were poorly represented. In another conclusive statement, the article calls for recognizing the diversity of actors in Ecuador and the importance of public debate, in which the media plays an important role. Mila Maldonado et al. (2024) present a clear summary of the issues and discussions that have taken place but do not analyse the framings beyond their content.

Another recent article is one written by Orellana & Orellana (2024). It uses the Yasuni referendum to approach and analyse James Scott's theory on the failure of modernist development projects. This article is relevant because it focuses on the referendum as a case study to analyse broader development theories, similar to the proposed thesis's approach. Orellana & Orellana (2024) present a critical theoretical analysis and conclude that the traditional notion of development has resulted in an oppressive ideal in the country due to the imposition of a single vision of the 'good life' based on material accumulation and the exclusion of other forms of well-being. The article argues that resistance to Western development - imposed by the State and at odds with local worldviews- triggers a backlash against grand development plans (Orellana & Orellana, 2024). In this article, the referendum is interpreted as a direct expression of citizens' will in the case of the Yasuni-ITT exploitation, which has generated intense debate and revealed a deep divide in development debates. The article argues that the positive vote in the referendum for the Yasuni-ITT represents a form of resistance to large extractive projects and modernisation and development plans (Orellana & Orellana, 2024).

Both Mila Maldonado et al. (2024) and Orellana & Orellana (2024) demonstrate Yasuni's importance in public debates and the country's social diversity. The articles show conflicting debates on development and an extended dialogue around the Yasuni and the 2023 referendum. This is key to this thesis study as it demonstrates the importance of the case in Ecuador and the richness of the debates (and narratives) present.

Espinosa (2013) and Le Queng (2013) are articles closely related to the subject but published earlier. They focus on the counter-extractivist discourse and imaginaries connected to the Yasuni-ITT Proposal.

Espinosa (2013) conducted a discourse analysis on and around the Yasuni-ITT Proposal. The article explores the unexpected emergence of the ITT initiative and the discursive strategies employed to support or oppose it. Main discourses favouring leaving the oil in the ground include arguments related to territoriality, cultural identity, biodiversity conservation, and climate change mitigation. The author argues that despite achieving discursive structuration, the proposal did not institutionalize fully, indicating an ambiguous form of hegemony and eventual failure of the proposal (Espinosa, 2013). This article comes closest to the present thesis; interestingly, it also acknowledges the initiative's discursive scope and the hegemonic nature of extractivist discourses. However, this article was published ten years ago, ignoring the development of the social movement and consequent referendum.

Furthermore, Le Quang (2016) examines the Yasuni-ITT Initiative as a catalyst for envisioning new societal imaginaries, particularly within the Ecuadorian constitution, biocentrism, and capitalism. The author argues that the initiative, prompted by concerns over limited oil reserves and climate change, sought to transition Ecuador toward a post-petroleum economy. Despite its multidimensional approach encompassing environmental, economic, and social aspects, the initiative faced challenges, particularly in international negotiations. Nevertheless, it marked a significant step towards reimagining Ecuadorian society beyond reliance on oil extraction. It encouraged reflection on societal values and habits, aiming to reduce dependence on oil and challenge the extractivist development model (Le Quang, 2016). These articles underscore the need for a broader discursive shift across local, national, and global arenas to secure long-term success for initiatives like Yasuni-ITT (Espinosa, 2013; Le Quang, 2016).

A research gap could be recognised after a literature review as no published articles focused on the Yasuni referendum and the role of counter-hegemonic narratives in a post-extractivist transformation were found. However, the articles presented above are essential to recognise the importance of this issue both nationally and internationally (Mila Maldonado et al., 2024). Articles such as Espinosa (2013), Le Quang (2016), and Mila Maldonado et al. (2024) have methodological or theoretical similarities to this thesis, highlighting that this research is relevant to current academic debates. Academic literature highlights the importance of discursive and public debate connected to the Yasuni case, reinforcing the need to focus on narratives and their role in society (Espinosa, 2013; Mila Maldonado et al., 2024; Orellana & Orellana, 2024). This comprehensive overview of the contextual landscape and State of the Art provides a solid foundation for understanding the dynamics at play in this study, setting the stage for the detailed exploration of results in the following section.

6 Results

The following section presents the results of the data analysis, organized according to the three sub-research questions. A constructivist grounded theory approach (Charmaz, 2017), combined with elements of narrative inquiry (Bochner & Herrmann, 2020), guided the analysis. Prominent and recurring themes were carefully examined, and multiple rounds of analysis were conducted to ensure the robust identification of categories, recognizing the inherent subjectivity of qualitative data analysis. Given the extensive information, results were synthesized and reduced to present the most recurring and prominent themes.

6.1 Sub-Research Question I: What key elements define the counter-hegemonic narratives around the 2023 Yasuni referendum?

The first sub-research question explored the narratives used by collectives and experts in the counter-hegemonic movement surrounding the Yasuní referendum. Investigating how the 2023 Yasuni referendum was framed provided insight into two key aspects: first, identifying which elements are most emphasized, revealing what participants perceive as most significant, and second, examining the specific language, terms, and expressions used to discuss these elements helped to understand the nature of the present narratives. Therefore, the data analysis focused on identifying recurrent themes and any distinctive framings that could shed light on the underlying narrative dynamics.

Findings suggest that respondents often situate the Yasuní referendum within a broader, complex context, reflecting the lack of clear boundaries between the referendum and the more significant socio-political issues at play. The research design considered this complexity, focusing on the local, national and social context rather than treating the referendum as an isolated case. Moreover, specific recurring linguistic patterns and shared symbolic meanings emerged across the data. This section's results are structured around six categories and the main elements that were part of the narratives on these topics: Yasuní, Local social elements, National dynamics, The state, The oil industry, and Structural factors.

6.1.1 Yasuni

The first category of results to the first sub-research question focuses on Yasuni. Results include the narratives about the referendum that took place in 2023 but primarily focus on the history leading up to the vote. When asked about the case, experts highlighted its complexity and emphasized the need to integrate it into the analysis. Another prominent element that was identified is the symbolic value that has been attributed to the Yasuni. Both aspects are presented in more detail below.

The Yasuni Referendum as embedded in a complex context with a long history

The analysis revealed several key themes in the narratives around the Yasuni referendum, including a clear understanding that the case is part of a more extended history, with several actors and different scales that must be considered when analyzing the Yasuni referendum. Most interviews and documents reiterated that one cannot look at the Yasuni referendum (or the Yasuni in general) in a vacuum. In fact, this would fall short and miss the importance of the context that led to the creation of the initiative, the social mobilization and struggle, and finally, the referendum to stop the oil exploitation in the ITT block of the Yasuni National Park in 2023. As one expert explained, *“I believe that the Yasuni referendum is the accumulation of a historical process in which several social subjects are very strongly present”* (E6).

In addition, several experts highlighted the need to consider all the actors present in this territory, listen to them, and make an effort to truly understand the loss of historical and cultural value that oil exploitation has meant in the past and could mean in the future.

“In other words, there is a value, beyond the concrete, beyond the symbolic in terms of extractivism, there is a cultural, historical, educational, hyper-important value in itself, which has never really been systematized, researched, which is destroyed by extractivism. Just like that, it is destroyed, it is lost, there are things that are so beautiful and so fantastic, so incredible. If you really go there, people can show you, and this also gets lost in these religious fights” (E7), one participant emphasized.

Interestingly, the Yasuni Region was often framed as a *“living territory”* where *“a series of political, social and cultural relations are tensed, intertwined and broken. That is, as if there, constantly within that territory, and what is around that territory, is in a movement of many tensions, many disruptions as well, and sometimes even violence”* (E4). This implies that Yasuni is a living organism with a deep understanding of the social-political ecologies present and how they coexist, conflict, and depend on each other.

To sum up, the data analysis highlighted that conserving the Yasuni is a complex and multifaceted challenge that defies simple or quick solutions. An expert further defended this point, explaining that only

by understanding the complexity and constant movement of social relations in the territory can the case be understood because

“Nothing that can happen there can be easily resolved. Nor is it solved with the referendum, nor with a free and informed prior consultation, nor with the territorial definition of the NAWA or the affected communities. In other words, nothing can be worked on individually, but it necessarily requires the articulation of the social actors that are present there, because they are always in tension or relation to each other” (E4).

The symbolism of Yasuni

A recurring topic during data analysis was the notion of the Yasuni case - and referendum- symbolic power. While the meanings given to this “symbol” are multiple, examining the symbolic significance attributed to the Yasuni is crucial to better understanding the narratives and framings surrounding it. Using a case as a symbol or representative element is a telling aspect of how people create narratives about the world and which elements take part in storytelling. Four overarching themes were present in the use of the Yasuni as a symbol: as a historical, plural process that connects social movements, as a symbol of other possibilities, the Amazon region as symbolic of environmentalism, and the referendum as a result of a longstanding struggle and a historic milestone.

First, the Yasuni was said to represent the result of a historical, plural process that connects several battles. It was pictured as *“a cause that unites”* at many scales, a *“polysemic,” “emblematic case,”* which is also a *“historical process.”* It represents a reason why different social actors have come together and is seen as *“one of the elements that marked national history, because in addition to that [Yasuni referendum], the different Amazonian communities and peoples, the environmental collectives, people from different backgrounds took on the challenge of proposing the popular consultation for Yasuni” (PC5).*

This symbolism also transcends the specific history that led to the Yasuni referendum but rather embodies *“multiple struggles that are taking place and that have been taking place in the past and that will continue to take place in the future concerning extractivisms, territories and peoples, nature and peoples” (E6).* The Yasuni cause brought together movements connected to different geographical areas: the predominantly urban academic with organised mobilisation, Indigenous peoples in their territories with the climate struggle, and rural communities with urban ones. This case also brings together local and national debate and even includes international discussions and accountability. Bringing social groups together is why YASUnidos, in its early stages, was defined as a *“movement of movements.”*

The Yasuni serves as a unifying cause, bringing together diverse thematic foci into a cohesive whole. The motivations to become part of the cause are manifold, with the most frequently mentioned being: defence of land, territory, and nature, cultural value and presence of Indigenous groups in isolation, social justice, rights of Indigenous peoples and nationalities, climate change, unique biodiversity and the *“best place to save the most species in the in the least amount of space of any place on the planet”* (E5), conservation for intrinsic value and not for money, against extractivism itself and specifically oil, desire for other modes of production and to continue the struggle and show disagreement. For example,

“We cannot stop the climate crisis if we do not protect the mega biodiversity that exists in our territory. We cannot stop the climate crisis if we do not protect those who protect this biodiversity, the peoples and nationalities present there. To say yes to life, to say yes to Yasuni, is to protect the peoples who are there, it is to protect nature, to protect all the mega biodiversity, it is to protect life itself, the continuity of all the peoples who are there” (PC3).

The embeddedness of the case to its history and context, the different motivations, and geographical scales were the basis for the Yasuni case to be framed as the *“defence of the common home,”* which is in the *“heart of the Amazon”* and a *“the last frontier.”* Furthermore, defending it is *“all about gaining solidarity,”* *“simple to understand what is actually important in life,”* and *“saying yes to life.”* There is a lot of embodied struggle and responsibility in the way people and collectives refer to the case, often saying, *“We are Yasuni.”*

Second, the Yasuni was often presented as a symbol of other possibilities. Results presented a recognition of how, among other things, the ITT Initiative was groundbreaking in its proposal, and the referendum was the first case of direct climate democracy worldwide. The perception of the Yasuni case was sometimes characterized as a form of *“concrete utopia.”* This was argued because the case went outside the norm by presenting other ways of decision-making processes and represented a departure from the hegemonic discourse of development. For example, one expert argued that *“after 50 years of oil extraction in Ecuador, the defence of Yasuni is also a concrete, possible, viable form, and comes from below as an initiative”* (E3). Additionally, an expert argued that the social movement that has accompanied the case is a *“symptom of change”* and explained that, while one singular case does not mean there is a post-extractivist transformation, the fact that the Yasuni struggle has been sustained for over a decade and won in a national referendum is a clear sign that there is – at least the wish for- social transformation. Several data sources reminded (me) of Ecuador's other referendums in the aftermath of the Yasuni ITT initiative and the request for a people's referendum by YASunidos.

Since the inception of the ITT Initiative, Yasuni has been more than just a forest—it has become a symbol of resistance, transformation, and the pursuit of new possibilities. As a result, Yasuni represents alternative imaginaries, new pathways, and a break from what is considered "normal" or hegemonic. The collective Yasunidos has embraced this symbolism, even coining the verb *yasunizar* (to yasunise) to signify that the movement extends beyond Yasuni as a physical place. Instead, it embodies a transformative action filled with motivation, resistance, and change. This is reflected in expressions found in the data, such as "*Yasunicemos el Ecuador*" (Let yasunice Ecuador), calling for a broader shift inspired by Yasuni's legacy.

Third, the Amazon Region or *Amazonia* itself has carried symbolic significance in the environmental movement, so it was seen as no coincidence that such an emblematic case like the Yasuni is placed in the Amazon Region. At the national level, *Amazonia* is seen as the birthplace of the environmental movement. This is not only where the environmental movement took its first steps. It is also where many figures, especially Indigenous women, who are prominent in environmental conservation come from and are known internationally. Likewise, this region was mentioned as "*our Amazonia*" and where "*the future lives*" as a way of recognising its ecological and natural value. An expert also pointed out that a strong symbolism of the Amazon and, more specifically, of tropical forests can be recognised in international climate discourses due to their high value for air purification, CO₂ fixation in the soil, and biodiversity, among other reasons.

Lastly, the 2023 Yasuni referendum and its positive results were also distinguished as symbolic. The referendum was seen as a "*historic milestone*" that showed Ecuadorians' desire for change. It was emphasized that this was the first national environmental referendum worldwide, which was seen as a historic opportunity to initiate international critical dialogue. Some data sources also identified the referendum as a positive step forward resulting from a longstanding struggle. Similarly, it was noted that the state's million-dollar campaign lost against a campaign that was, at its core, simple, with few funds, and mostly contained clear and short messages.

Moreover, some interviewees and press conferences expressed no surprise with the referendum results, saying that "*there is a lot of environmental awareness*" and "*environmental vocation*" in Ecuador. Hence, "*the referendum would have already won in 2013*". Two interviewees elaborated on this, explaining that the government's blocking of the referendum in 2013 was also symbolic because the work put into it showed that the president himself thought that a people's referendum could win. For the interviewees, this represented the power of organized social mobilisation and the interests and power behind oil

exploitation in the Yasuni. To complement this, an interviewee expressed that it is interesting how, after over a decade, the Yasuni referendum still won, despite the time passed, other struggles that have risen, and all the young people who reached voting age in the meantime.

Nonetheless, three interviewees were cautious about portraying the Yasuní referendum as solely a positive or world-changing event. Not only did two interviews express surprise with the results due to the prominence of the pro-oil discourse in Ecuador, but several interviews recognized that the referendum's impact is limited. They argued that the ITT is “*only one block*” of the relatively large scale of oil exploitation in the Amazon region. It was also highlighted that the referendum lost at the local level, which means that the majority of Ecuador voted ‘Yes’ and only in two provinces of the Amazon region did the ‘No’ vote win. For experts, this stands for the dependence on the oil industry created at the local level, as well as a loss at the level of the social movement and argumentation power against this extractive industry.

Finally, interviewees were cautious, saying that the “*referendum can be a double-edged sword*” used by the government to distract with a symbolic victory while otherwise advancing other agendas. For this reason, the data presented several instances calling for fulfilling the mandate, as the referendum should become a reality and not only remain a democratic victory.

6.1.2 Local Social Elements

The next category from the analysis focused on the narratives about local social elements, especially their interaction with the oil industry and territorial struggle. These narratives primarily reflect on the experiences of living close to the oil exploitation rather than focusing on the ITT block specifically. Here, the central theme focused on Indigenous groups, although there was also mention of the church's role in the Amazonia, both of which will be presented next.

Indigenous Groups

Experts consistently emphasized that indigenous groups are the most affected by the oil industry. Consequently, the conservation of Yasuni National Park is closely connected to respecting their rights and ways of life. This prompted a closer examination of the narratives employed by these social groups. As only one expert interview was done with a person living in the Yasuni and who belongs to an Indigenous community, the complementary data sources were key to further understanding their narratives and experiences.

A key narrative from the analysis was the deep connection to land and territory that Indigenous worldviews have. In their way of sharing, a sense of fundamental meaning and attachment to the territory and its human and non-human forms of life was present. This code was called *territoriality* and connected instances when this profound relationship with their lands and territories was expressed. Territoriality, in this case, represents this deep and intrinsic relationship that has been developed in several Indigenous worldviews to their land, for example, in the way they talked about the Yasuni by constantly calling it “*our ancestral territory*,” “*living territory*,” “*defence of our land*,” “*our home*,” instead of the ITT block or Yasuni National Park. Additionally, there was a constant reminder of the presence of groups in voluntary isolation when talking about the defence of the Yasuni. Indigenous groups in voluntary isolation were said to be part of “*our family*,” “*brothers*,” and “*partners*” in need of protection, reflecting the historical experiences of colonization and struggle that Indigenous peoples have experienced. Nature is also highly valued as part of their family; as one Indigenous leader said, “*People live here, be it animals, fish, persons, groups in isolation. They are our families*” (PC5). Therefore, “*Yasuni is our home, our place, our house, our territory. Here we see women who are behind us, they have walked, we continue to walk. We have left our children, our families to raise our voices*” (PC5).

Another important narrative connected to Indigenous groups was the feeling of being in constant struggle. From the era of colonization to the modern-day exploitation of natural resources on their territories, Indigenous peoples have faced the continuous dispossession of their territories. Hence, an embodiment of lived history was demonstrated. Some of the framings that represent this were: “*We are standing up in struggle*,” “*this struggle is thousands of years old*,” and “*our daily struggle*.” Similarly, an identification with the struggle and a determination to continue it was present, as a leader declared, “*I will continue to fight to the very end*” (PC3) or in the way NAWÉ documents are signed with “*we are Waorani, we are the resistance*.”

The narrative surrounding interactions with oil companies and the emotions tied to these encounters emerged as another key theme in the analysis. Experts unanimously agreed that Indigenous communities are the first ones impacted by oil extraction, facing significant social, cultural, health, and environmental consequences in their bodies and territories. There was also broad consensus regarding the absence of prior, informed consultation and the lack of opportunities for meaningful participation in decision-making processes. Accordingly, Indigenous communities expressed feelings of powerlessness against the losses they have experienced. Some reasons shared are low economic resources, difficulty contacting territories within oil fields, difficulty protesting against the companies, difficulty in sharing their history outside of

the local scale, divisions created between groups, and the power that companies and states have in the territory. One expert explained how,

“In times of problems, be it a protest for something, for non-compliance, or the impotence of the company, the Waorani make the decision to go on strike. And they fight with ‘community relations,’ but they do not fight with the owner of the circus (...). The owners of the companies are there, either in Miami, North America or Europe and not here” (E8).

In this context, a dilemma arises between conserving indigenous traditions, culture, and life forms against the desire to belong more to the “modern” world to have more means of resistance. For example, one person expressed the desire to have more scientific knowledge, funding, and international allies to stand a chance in protecting their community.

Role of the Church

Interviews revealed both shared and conflicting views on the church's role within the Yasuni region. On the one side, there was a recognition of the influence of the church in *Amazonia* with a critical perspective on the history of how this influence was obtained. One expert explained that *“there is a long history of very strong religious colonialism in the whole of the Amazonia”* (E7). There was also an acknowledgment of the process of dispossession of territories in which the church helped and how it reflects the state's vision of nature and ownership of the territory. One expert expressed it very clearly, saying:

“And here comes the summer language institutes and all that, right? While the missions are conquering us, socialising us, and everything. At the same time, the state, as there was a little bit of territorial space left, wrongly called ‘selva baldía,’⁸ let the oil companies occupy it; they entered for free” (E8).

Conversely, one expert admitted the church's current role as a promoter of social projects and an ally to local communities. Its influence lies in the extensive network of ecclesiastical actors in the Amazon Region that has been built over time, from episcopal territories, other institutions- such as Caritas, REPAM⁹, PUAM¹⁰- and the ownership of radio stations. One expert pointed out that *“the Church was a very relevant social actor in the Amazonian territory and, in fact, accompanied the gestation of many social processes, so here especially highlighting the history of Aguarico, the mobilisations, the strikes, the seizures of the roads demanding better living conditions”* (E4) and explaining that there is now a part of the Church working with the approach of promoting, guaranteeing, and the enforceability of human rights. According

⁸ No direct translation, something like wasteland forest, no-man land, vacant land, uncultivated land or abandoned land.

⁹ Pan-Amazonian Ecclesial Network

¹⁰ Amazon University Programme

to this expert, the church has taken a favourable position on environmentalism because of the encyclical *Laudato Si'*¹¹, encyclical *Laudato Deum*¹², and the growing conversation regarding eco-theology and eco-conversion. The church was, in fact, also present at the campaign for the Yasuni in 2023.

6.1.3 National Dynamics

Another key element in the counter-hegemonic narratives in the collected data was the connection of the Yasuni referendum to specific social dynamics at a national scale. In contrast to the localness of the case in terms of impacts and infrastructure, the discussion about it has expanded to wider scales. Social elements at the national level were considered important due to the role of nationwide movements in advocating for the conservation of the ITT block and the referendum to ban oil exploitation in Yasuni National Park.

Social Movements

A straightforward and positive framing concerning social movements and their role in the case could be recognised. The narratives often indicated affirmative elements of bottom-up mobilisation and highlighted the benefits of initiating debate at the societal level. In a few instances, data suggested that social movements provide a space for critical debate, establishing countercultures, and empowering individuals. This was deemed an essential element of the Yasuni case, especially for the symbolical meaning it acquired by being an entry point to societal debates and creating collective ideals. For example, conserving Yasuni for its intrinsic value and not for money was a proposal that was created through debate “from below” in contrast to the initial proposal that focused on getting financial compensation.

YASunidos' role in realizing a referendum, bringing attention to the case, and sustaining the struggle for over a decade was also acknowledged. One expert shared that *“the result of that [the referendum] was that [positive], thanks to the persistence and the patience and the capacity, I would say professional, of the lawyers of YASunidos”* (E1).

However, discrepancies between social and environmental moments were also acknowledged. They were divided on issues such as the level of criticism towards capitalism, modes of production, focus on the

¹¹ “Laudato Si’ is an encyclical of Pope Francis published in May 2015. It focuses on care for the natural environment and all people, as well as broader questions of the relationship between God, humans, and the Earth” (Rice, 2022).

¹² Laudato Deum is an apostolic exhortation by Pope Francis, published in 2023. It emphasizes urgent action on climate change and environmental action, building on encyclical Laudato Si’ (Francis, 2023).

economy, and desires for economic development, among others. Nevertheless, as said before, the Yasuni has been a cause capable of unifying diverse social and environmental movements.

Environmental-Social Awareness

During the expert interviews, repeated comments about the social and environmental awareness of the broad population were present. Especially with a focus on which groups have more or less sensibility to certain topics and suggestions of why this could be the case. Experts often cited the disaggregated Yasuni referendum results across different geographical scales—often linked to varying socio-economic strata—as evidence to support their arguments.

Some experts agreed that there is high environmental and social awareness in Ecuador, or environmental “vocation,” as many call it. Perceptions of environmental awareness were connected to the lived history of specific sectors. For example, popular sectors and their experience of historical neglect from the state, Indigenous and Amazonian peoples who are in constant struggle and suffer from the direct effects of extraction, urban sectors because of their vulnerability to the climate crisis, and young people because of their awareness of climate change.

“And after the Yasuní issue, other consultations took place; it clearly shows that the Ecuadorian population is highly sensitive to environmental issues, and it is the popular and lower middle-class sectors who support this proposal to say yes to life with an enormous awareness of climate change and also with a very clear idea that it is better to save the forest than to have money.” (E3)

Social and environmental awareness results showed a comprehension of negative ecology-economy relationships. In other words, the data collected showed a vision that a better economy in the current development concept often means destroying nature. As most people do not benefit from a higher gross internal product (GDP) or the profits of extractivism, they only experience the destruction of nature and their livelihoods. This goes hand in hand with a deep understanding of how little benefit oil has brought both locally and nationally. In the data, phrases beginning with “*after 50 years of oil exploitation...*” were frequently found to recount the impacts or the few benefits that have been seen. Representing a sense of disbelief in the promises of development connected to oil extraction.

Water was another topic that came up in conversations about awareness. Water holds a lot of symbolic and practical importance for Ecuadorians, a country where most people depend on agriculture, and ancient worldviews deem water and water bodies sacred. Interviewees reminded me that nowadays, there are sectors in Ecuador where water is scarce, and historically, the fights and divisions over water

have been prominent. This is one of the reasons why a need or even urgency to act in the face of the climate emergency was identified. Experts explained that in the current situation, *“it is total nonsense”* to think of continuing exploitation that pollutes water—also connected with broader questions such as *“if humanity cannot make a conscious decision to conserve this [the most biodiverse place on earth], what will we conserve? What will we save?”* (E5).

When experts said there is little environmental or social awareness in the country, this mainly referred to the concentration of academic critical discourse in specific spheres, the visions shared among higher classes, or the prominence of modern/western lifestyles. In terms of specific spheres, there was recognition that the academic branches that maintain critical positions on the extractivist system or other visions favourable to the Yasuni are few and concentrated into very specific groups. This argument was also complemented by an explanation that environmentalism has been presented in a negative and radical discourse from politics, which could be a factor in why some people disengage from the case. Additionally, some experts argued that high socioeconomic classes present little environmental sensitivity due to the privilege and lack of difficulties connected to access to natural resources. For example, one expert explained that,

“There are things that they [higher classes] do not understand because their privilege clouds them, no matter how much information and education they have at some university. On the other hand, when you go into popular sectors and you ask, ‘What has oil given you? ‘People say ‘nothing, ‘full stop.’” (E3).

Lastly, experts argued that the lack of social-environmental awareness is primarily influenced by Western or modern lifestyles and mentalities, significantly impacting Ecuador. Experts focused on the predominance of modernist life to explain how difficult it is to confront the hegemonic narrative, as it is embedded even in people's everyday lives. Two experts argued that Western lifestyles and mentalities have gained influence in the country since its colonial times and have stayed up to present times.

Nowadays, wishes for Western-oriented development and lifestyles are a common element in Ecuador that has been incorporated into global capitalist markets and politically strives for economic gain. Experts said *“development”* is often understood as economic gain and an *“idea of personal success being deeply linked to money.”* Interview responses consistently highlighted the rise of individualism in modern society, leading to seeking one's benefits before those of others or the community. Similarly, since the focus is on economic gain, it was said that a *“short-term memory”* often leads to a focus on immediate results without thinking about the long-term consequences or the lessons learned from the past.

Moreover, discussions with experts provided valuable perspectives on how this modern individualistic mentality creates and sustains preconceptions of the Amazon Region and a disconnection – geographic and emotional- to the impacts produced by the oil industry. Several experts shared how their perceptions and positions changed after having a face-to-face experience with the *Amazonia*. An expert shared that,

“As long as it is far away in this other place, in this other territory, in this inhospitable place, where I only imagine that there are monkeys, toucans, plants, and there are no people; there are no conflicts, I do not care what exists there, as long as there is oil so that my car can move here so that I can have my electricity cable. I still feel that we have not managed to break that which would help us to connect and understand, because what happens over there will definitely affect me here too, even if I live in Quito or if I live in Guayaquil” (E4)

6.1.4 The State

A significant category identified was the state, including how it is perceived by experts and in documents and its role, interests, and influence. This perception of the state can be considered a key aspect of the counter-hegemonic narrative because it informs on the perception of the state as a traditionally hegemonic actor, thereby aligning closely with the focus of this research. Note that government officials change over time; the data analysis considered this and focused on narratives that referred to continued feelings and perceptions towards the state rather than elements specific to the government in power.

Generally, a rather negative connotation of the state was present, including feelings of distrust and tiredness. Data showed repeated comments about corruption, the state as an actor that does not care about local impacts, has failed to keep its promises, is focused only on economic gain, and responds to the interest of selected people and industries. The data showed frustration over the state's historical neglect of some populations and the empty promises made over time, especially those connected to the myth of development. As one expert commented,

“50 years later, oil has not fulfilled those great promises of resolving poverty, inequality, abandonment by the state, right? The Amazonian territories have the worst indices in terms of health, education, road access, etcetera.”(E3).

Moreover, the feeling was not only about the failure to fulfil the state's promises but also about it not being very important for the state.

“If, in theory, they create these jobs to give them [local communities], but we do not know the implications for the health of these people, it does not matter. The state does not care; the company does not care. It is enough for them to say that they generate and mobilise the economy” (E4), stressed one expert.

The state was thus characterised as an actor that maintains a mainstream discourse focused on economic development. Experts criticised the focus on monetary gains and disagreed with the idea that there are “sacrificial places,” which is often the dominant vision shared by state policies. Regarding the pro-extractive discourses, one expert explained that

“There is this ongoing expansion of oil, and there is, and with absolutely every administration that comes into power, there is some talk about how the economy could benefit by augmenting the amount of oil extraction. And, of course, that means moving farther and farther east and southward in Yasuni” (E5).

In addition, the state's role in connection to extractivism was one of use of power in decision-making and control over territories, repression towards signs of opposition, and strategic information management. Some sentences shared that demonstrated this are: “They try to confuse us” or “They try to put fear into the population.” When talking about the management of information, “data that is strongly discrepant between various sources and continue to be so and in some cases they [reports] have been politically manipulated,” “falsehood has been demonstrated.” For these reasons, a loss of credibility in the state discourse was revealed.

A final important element in connection to the Yasuni referendum and the state is the significance of the insistence on oil exploitation and the unwillingness to back down. The state was portrayed as desperate for revenue, refusing to take even a single step away from its extractive agenda. This is particularly striking given that Yasuni-ITT is only one oil block with declining reserves.

6.1.5 The Oil Industry

Another significant category was the oil industry, including how experts and documents perceive it. The perception of the oil industry can be considered another key element in a counter-hegemonic narrative, which examines the oil industry as an actor that traditionally benefits from the hegemonic narrative.

The characterization of the oil industry was often presented in abstract and distant terms, often like a machine and system in perpetuate motion to achieve its goal: Extraction. Again, comments on corruption and lack of interest in local impacts were present. The industry was described as parasitic; one that “entered for free” and “grabbed” the land, later changing social dynamics and creating division in local communities and economic dependencies. Two experts remarked that, due to the state’s historical abandonment of populations in Amazonia, oil companies gain great control and influence at a local level by adopting a state-like role in the territory. One example reads:

“there was a kind of populist policy from Repsol that gave them [group leaders] what they wanted, which were usually luxury consumer goods for the leaders, like television screens, or an internet connection so they could watch programs in Amazonia and things like that, without improving in any way living conditions.” (E1)

A prominent theme in the data was the oil industry's various social, environmental and political impacts. The impacts that were named correlate with those found in academic literature, presented section 5.2.3. This shows a high level of awareness of the impacts of oil exploitation. Table 4 summarizes the impacts mentioned in the data.

Table 4: Oil Exploitation Impacts Reflected in the Collected Data

Impact Category	Impacts	
Environmental	Oils spills	Land degradation and land use shifts
	Deforestation	Biodiversity loss
	Air, soil, and water pollution	Forest fragmentation
	Induced climate change through fossil fuel emissions	Loss of healthy ecosystems for future generations
	Soil erosion	
Social	Poverty and precariousness	Consumption of polluted water
	Health problems	Little or no access to basic services
	Deaths/threads to nature protectors	Normalization of violence
	Poor living conditions	Gender inequalities and violence
Cultural	Territorial dispossession	In-migration / Arrival of settlers
	Abandonment of traditional Indigenous economic activities and disengagement with the territory	Territorial disputes of contacted and uncontacted Indigenous groups
	Changes in cultural habits and identity transformations	Communication often through intermediation or translation
	Conflicts among Indigenous groups due to clientelism from oil companies	Loss of unity and conflicts within communities
	Difficulty in domestic activities	Destruction of places of spiritual value
Political	Lack of environmental monitoring, information and transparency	Oil companies replace/take the role of the state
	Lack of social monitoring	Clientelism and corruption
	Lack of participation	Limitation information
	No reparation for social impacts or pollution	
Economic	Dependence on the company but without investment in further economic development	Territorial dispossession and unequal distribution of oil benefits
	Departure from the area by the company without reparation/compensation	Precarious jobs without social security

In particular, the changes in the way of life created by the contact with oil companies, roads, and the monetary market are effects that, once changed, there is no turning back and have high social and

environmental impacts. Data often reminded that all impacts would not be remedied simply by the exit of the oil company or the closure of a block, as one expert explained:

“The communities become dependent on the oil companies, and when the oil companies leave, the communities are left with nothing. And the state, as it has never been there, is not there to fill this role that the oil companies assign themselves.” (E2)

Another important aspect in narratives on the oil industry was the infrastructure—mainly highways and gas flares. On the one hand, infrastructure was seen as a bridge between the industry's abstract and distant aspects and the concrete signs of its presence. On the other hand, experts elaborated on the side effects of such infrastructure and highlighted how it is now fixed to the land and cannot be removed easily.

An intriguing aspect of how the oil industry is framed in the data is the frequent use of company names when discussing the industry. Instead of referencing zones, oil block numbers, or specific block names, experts and complementary data sources tend to say the company's name operating in an oil block. In all the sources analysed, one finds phrases such as: *“We had a very strong discussion with Petro [Petroecuador]”, “In Block 16 of Repsol”, “...because Texaco made an environmental disaster there”, “Repsol, while it was working in Ecuador...”, “what Texaco did in the Amazon in the 70s, 80s is a crime”.*

The frequent use of companies' names has been an important and almost symbolic aspect in framing the industry. On the one hand, it is noteworthy how oil companies are repeatedly referred to as if they own the land inside a block. On the other hand, the names are often connected to the impacts created by these companies, suggesting a notion of accountability or a way for people to put a name to an industry that is otherwise quite abstract to them as it is not easy to contact.

6.1.6 Structural Elements

A final significant theme during data analysis was *structural elements*, which were repetitively brought up during expert interviews. The topic of structural elements was brought up in two main contexts: the first one was as a layer of contextualization needed to understand the case and hegemonic discourses, and the second one was as an explanation of why it is challenging to achieve a post-extractivist transformation or in which way narratives are an important element, yet not enough. Both contexts are essential to answer the question proposed in this thesis as it was a prominent element in the diverse narratives analysed, which sheds light on how counter-hegemonic narratives understand hegemonic structures.

Some experts commented on the importance of more people understanding structural connections to raise awareness and said they would like to see more debate on modes of production, global relations, modern ways of life, or historical dependencies, among others listed in more detail in Figure 5 below. This element of the results could demonstrate both a limitation of narratives and their central role in identifying what elements do not or do not allow social change.

Figure 5: Structural elements mentioned in the data

6.2 Sub-Research Question II: How do these narratives envision a post-extractivist transformation?

The previous sub-question focused on prominent themes and framings in the narratives around the Yasuni referendum. Building on the above results, this sub-research question examines how present narratives envision a post-extractive transformation. The analysis of the results for this question focused primarily on experts' responses to the direct question about whether a post-extractivist transformation is present or possible, along with document analysis of plans and proposals.

It is important to note that part of this question was answered in the previous section, as several experts emphasized the importance of raising social-environmental awareness and the limitations due to structural elements in a post-extractivist transformation. Likewise, the responses presented below were often linked to the context or social elements of the case, which were also discussed in the previous section. Another recurring element in this question was the symbolism of the Yasuní case, mainly how it represents other possibilities. Apart from that, the responses were mostly related to a national (and sometimes international) transition.

This question is more abstract and subjective compared to the previous one. Nevertheless, the results were systematically categorized into three primary categories: debating the possibility of a post-

extractivist transformation, what would be needed to promote such transformation, and concrete wishes/desires for the future. For all of these, there were two levels of analysis: thematic, when explicitly stated, and interpretative, from the framings and narratives used in other answers.

6.2.1 Debating the Possibility of a Post-Extractivist World

The following section presents the results of discussions on the possibility of societal transformation, structured around two central themes: reasons to maintain hope and discouraging elements.

Reasons to Maintain Hope

Some experts shared a positive view on the possibility of a post-extractivist transition. These opinions were mainly connected to elements presented in the first research question, including the recognition that crude oil is running out, positive results of environmental referendums in Ecuador, and the loss of credibility of the hegemonic pro-extractivist discourse.

One expert explained that the failure of the extractive and capitalist model is impending, and sooner or later, a more extensive public might recognize it. This links to other results of RQ1, such as the clarity of extraction impacts and the feeling that the state has not delivered on its promises even *“50 years after oil exploitation started.”* Hinting that a sense of weariness is beginning to set in as the myth of development materializes. Likewise, a similar sentiment was shared about the results of the referendum, interpreting them as a desire of the population to look for alternatives to oil exploitation in contrast to the hegemonic-extractive discourse.

An expert shared how their hope lies in seeing the social movement present in the country,

“There are other spaces, CONAIE, [Indigenous] Peoples and Nationalities, YASunidos and a lot of other organisations that were also deployed around the referendum campaign, that believe that the country is not going to move forward, nor are the big problems going to be solved by reproducing an extractive model, because basically it is a model that proposes that there are territories that can be sacrificed, a population that can be sacrificed, and a country that needs these resources, and since the country needs these resources, it does not matter what happens to the peoples and nationalities, or the jungle, or the water.”(E3)

On a similar line, there was a reminder of other positive examples in this area that could signify a movement toward post-extractivist transformation and other positive examples that could be reproduced. Some of them were Costa Rica’s development model based on biodiversity, the victory of other environmental referendums, Colombia’s moratorium on oil expansion, and The Fossil Fuel Non-

Proliferation Treaty Initiative. Two experts reflected on how positive examples broaden possibilities and foster hope for achieving an integral societal transformation. One expert shared their reflection on history,

“There have been different moments in history when there have been general changes in production when there have been ways of re-inventing the world. Nobody imagined a world without slaves in classical Rome. Colonialism was not imagined as a way of producing agricultural products in Latin America without slavery. And now we cannot imagine a way to move around the planet or to manufacture certain compounds without massively damaging the water. But all we can do is agree that it has to be done differently, and it will be done.”(E0)

Therefore, data showed instances where elements of hope were present. Hope was expressed in elements such as people's capacity to dialogue, learn from each other, and show solidarity. Experts shared that they feel hope in the possibility of changing the system from within. Some experts also elaborated on their hope for democracy, reminding that it is important to regain trust and find *“elements that democratise democracy,”* such as the direct democracy of the Yasuní referendum. So, regaining trust in democracy was an element of hope, especially exemplified by one's capacity to *“be part of the change,”* or in YASunidos' campaign that emphasized how protecting the Yasuni was *“putting society in motion,”* calling to *“be part of the change and join the campaign.”* Hope was also seen as an element that is not easily lost and motivates more than fear. With this, an expert shared that:

“I think there is hope. We are not in a situation where all is lost. If we continue with the same behaviour as we have had for the last 100 years, we will reach a desperation situation very soon. But we will need some perspective that there is Hope. I will refer to a quote from Greta Thunberg. She basically said that we always need hope, and where there is action, there is always hope. But without that action, you know, she is implying that, okay, we can, we can talk a lot, we can have, you know, another ten meetings in the Copenhagen kind of tradition. And it may or may not mean anything. But if we can call to action, then something can be done. (E5)

Discouraging Elements

Nonetheless, during the data analysis, some discouraging elements became clear or led experts to share a negative view on the possibility of a just and fair post-extractivist transformation. These elements mostly referred to how difficult it is to change the hegemonic structures in place, like the ones presented in section 6.1.6 above. They especially commented on the state's reluctance to radically change some things, recalling that the referendum's popular mandate has not yet been fulfilled, nor have there been clear signs that this will happen soon.

Experts stressed how the history of Yasuni demonstrates how the state maintains an interest in monetary gain without much interest in controversies present or impacts on society. They also shared their concern

with the transition from oil exploitation to mining exploitation that has taken place in the country, pointing out the significant impacts of this industry and how it would be harmful to society to move from one extractivist model to the next. Interviewees stressed the need to change the extractivist model from its core but acknowledged that extractivism is resilient, powerful, and adaptable. Two experts expressed their doubts with broad questions such as, *“If there has been no such change so far, how can we know that it will happen?”* or *“Change might be happening, but is it fast enough?”*

Indigenous communities also shared discouraging feelings, such as constant struggle and powerlessness from their experiences of oppression from the extractivist mindset. Moreover, some experts also discussed the current crisis that the country is facing and the difficulties it poses in a transformation. Referring, for example, to how;

“The narrative and discourse of internal war and organised crime make even people who voted for Yasuní say’ no, but now we are at war, we have to use these resources and what a shame for the animals and what a shame for the people, but we are at war. It is either that or they kill my family’ (E6).

Similarly, an expert expressed how difficult imagining the future can be when the present is uncertain since *“we are at a time in the world where uncertainty organises our lives, war here, war here.”* Further sharing a reflection that *“Now we are witnessing a posthumous moment where we ask ourselves until when? And that until when, that uncertainty of until when do I have water, until when do I have life, until when can I have a job is constantly there” (E3).* They additionally said that thinking about the future is in itself a privilege and share an example:

“It seems to me that it is very difficult to talk to the young people of this country who have been abandoned. Let us say this is one of the generations, the second generation, I think, abandoned by the government, by society, criminalised if you are a racialised young person if you were born in Guayaquil if you were born in Esmeraldas, where there are no employment possibilities, no education possibilities, no guarantees of absolutely nothing, not even that you will have a life. Talking to young people about the future is difficult. But instead, we can talk about the here and now, and to talk about the here and now is to say: this is what you can do today” (E3).

6.2.2 What would be needed to achieve a post-extractivist transition?

The data analysis also identified several instances where specific framework conditions were highlighted as essential for facilitating a societal transformation, such as a transition to post-extractivism. Understanding the requirements for a post-extractivist transition—or what it takes to move beyond extractivism—emerged as a recurring theme. While experts and the data pointed to various necessary

conditions, three were consistently emphasized and widely agreed upon: fostering national awareness and dialogue, envisioning viable alternatives, and engaging in long-term planning.

Fostering National Awareness and Dialogue

Several instances occurred where experts expressed their desire for more awareness and dialogue as a central element that could prompt social transformation. This desire was connected to the importance of socio-environmental awareness, preconceptions about the Amazon region, disconnection to the negative impacts, and the impactful face-to-face experience with the local context as catalysts or inhibitors of social change. Experts commented that changes in mentality are possible *“when it moves your head or your heart,”* when an effort is made to step out of the comfort zone, and when a moment of reflection is taken to understand contexts beyond the simple stories being told. This was deemed an essential part of achieving a post-extractivist transformation, as it opened the possibilities and priorities of one's future.

Two experts elaborated on the nature of national debate and awareness, describing them as dynamic and ever-evolving. This dynamism makes them shapable; national public opinion is *“a historical process, and like history, it has changes, nuances, and contexts”* (E6). Similarly, there was the reflection that *“it has changed a lot over the years. There is no such thing as a static position because it also depends on who is in power, the discourses and narratives they use and position”* (E6).

Experts agreed that sustained, critical environmental and post-extractivist debate has not reached the mainstream level yet. Some argued that such critical reflections only rarely reach the national debate, often connected to moments of environmental crisis—like floods, wildfires, landslides, oil spills, and others—and evaporate after a while, calling out that *“we Ecuadorians have a short-term memory”*. Therefore, experts argue that the socioenvironmental national debate must get started and be actively fuelled to create a critical, socially and environmentally aware population.

According to the data analysed, such debate should be intercultural and interdisciplinary to be fair and fruitful for everyone. In terms of interculturality, it was highlighted that *“Interculturality in a plurinational country is a condition that must permeate all relations in society and must be reflected in laws and public policies.”* (A5). Intercultural dialogue was key in respecting Indigenous rights and voices and confronting preconceptions. One should focus on *“being able to understand these needs, and being able to put together something that is in line with what they [Indigenous communities] are asking to have, not what we think they have to have, because we Westerners are always going to have an ideal of what they have to do, how they have to do it, etcetera”* (E4). Such dialogue was also seen as a condition for cooperation

and an opportunity to learn from each other, because *“in the Amazon, there are certain places that are so important - because they allow us to learn and live in a different way- that we have to preserve, conserve, and better yet study and learn from them”* (E7). Recognizing the value of different ways of life, worldviews, and the richness of Indigenous knowledge in Ecuador.

In addition, experts shared their wish for science to be better listened to and included in policy-making and national debate. Academics especially shared that they want better communication with civil society and policy-making processes. There was a desire for policy to be made in direct democracy that listens to the knowledge and needs of all. The state's power in policymaking was also recognised, whereby two experts said it is important for the environmental debate to reach those circles.

Envisioning Viable Alternatives and Long-term Planning

Another theme was the need to think, formulate, and envision alternatives. Both experts and documents, especially plans and proposals prepared by collectives, explained that some societal transitions happen all the time. Hence, the discussion is more about deciding to actively participate in the transformation and its form rather than whether there is a societal transformation at all.

Data argued that much motivation comes from actively considering what the future could or should be like and how that is achievable. Experts reflected on how proposed plans show *“that there were actually alternatives”* to exploiting the oil in the ITT block, in contrast to the hegemonic narrative that commits to the idea that there is no alternative to exploitation. Two experts elaborated on this on a personal level, explaining how positive examples and the clarity of having alternatives are motivation to be involved in the movement. They also highlighted the need to keep asking *“broader questions than the closing of the ITT,”* arguing for the interconnectedness of the case to a bigger system, modes of production, and the impacts of the oil and extractive industry in other regions.

Long-term comprehensive planning was a second recurring aspect mentioned by experts and analysed in documents debating forms of achieving a post-extractivist transformation. It was reminded that social mobilization has the power to pressure transition but only gets concretized when it is accompanied by precise and comprehensive planning.

Experts shared how they wish planning offices would consider key elements that cannot be transformed, such as the impending end of oil resources and climate change impacts. Moreover, they shared that *“We need to somehow think about the Ecuador of the future”* rather than relying on reactionary and short-term strategies. Data stressed the country's deep-rooted economic and social crisis, which is only

worsened by the lack of a clear strategy to transition toward an equitable and sustainable role in the global economy. As a result, it was argued that government policies must go beyond simply resolving the fiscal deficit.

One expert focused on the importance of *“having a horizon”* or a goal to follow, arguing that only then can one start walking in a concrete direction. In other words:

“A necessary condition is to have a long-term vision, a plan, and a model to guide us on where to go and what path to follow. We cannot rely on the laws of the market—a fictional concept that does not exist—to somehow, by coincidence, improve Ecuador’s living conditions while it drifts in adverse waters because that simply will not happen” (E1).

In sum, a post-extractivist transformation requires awareness to ignite the will for change and the ability to envision alternative futures that challenge dominant paradigms. However, these aspirations remain incomplete without the concrete steps of long-term planning, ensuring that transformative possibilities move from vision to reality.

6.2.3 Concrete Wishes and Proposals for the Future

Throughout the data, proposals or wishes for the future were shared. These provide clear and specific examples demonstrating how the different actors interviewed and analysed from other documentation envision a post-extractivist transformation. Since each expert and data source had its focus on wishes for the future, the list is somewhat extensive; a more detailed compilation of answers can be seen in Table 5.

Some proposals worth highlighting include a moratorium on oil exploitation, stopping the expansion of the extraction frontier in the Amazon region, regulating the use of gas flares, and halting the construction of roads. Also directed at the oil industry, wishes to create better social-ecological standards and technology to reduce impacts on local communities and the environment were shared.

Indigenous communities shared desires that explicitly requested meaningful participation, the fulfilment of people’s mandate to close the ITT block, and an end to being instrumentalized. They also raised important questions, bringing attention to the fact that any transition must consider the communities already impacted and the dependencies that have been created. For them, this is a crucial point, as the focus should be on stopping exploitation and developing a comprehensive strategy for social and environmental reparations.

Economic alternatives were also proposed, emphasizing the redistribution of wealth, acknowledgment of ecological debt, and economic models based on biodiversity, such as community-based tourism,

biomedicine, bioindustry, and food sovereignty. The proposals envision a more equitable society focusing on small-scale and community-based production.

Table 5: Selection of wishes and proposals for a post-extractivist future found in data

Oil extraction	→	Moratorium on roads, gas flares, and oil frontier expansion
	→	Social and environmental reparations
	→	Improving social and environmental standards
Indigenous communities	→	Have active and meaningful participation.
	→	Yasuni ITT people's mandate to be fulfilled
	→	Ensure the protection of territories.
	→	Reparations
Protection of Democracy	→	Stop being instrumentalized
	→	Right to protest and resistance.
	→	Democracy without corruption regains trust in democracy.
Social equality and justice	→	Direct democracy mechanisms
	→	Equitable transformations, no sacrificable places or people
	→	Respecting the rights of nature, as stated in the constitution
	→	Protection of human rights (and Indigenous communities)
Re-think economic models	→	Respecting interculturality and plurinational state
	→	Focus on food sovereignty and self-sufficiency.
	→	Transition towards an equitable and sustainable development model based on biodiversity conservation
	→	Redistribution of wealth, fair taxation systems
	→	Recognition of ecological debt from the Global North
	→	Strengthening local economies
	→	Recycling and mineral recovery, Electrification of public transport

6.3 Sub-Research Question III: What significance do stakeholders within counter-extractivist movements attribute to narratives?

The objective of the third sub-research question was to understand experts' and collectives' perceptions of the significance of counter-hegemonic narratives in challenging dominant discourses and fostering social change, or more punctually, a post-extractivist transformation. All experts were asked at some point during their interviews how they perceive the role of narratives, making this the primary source of information for the results. However, prior research questions also significantly informed the findings. The final sub-research question integrates previously presented results while introducing a level of interpretative data analysis. The following section is divided into three main categories. First, there will be a summary of the perceived role of narratives. Then, two main topics from data analysis will be presented in more detail in sections 6.3.2, *The Past and the Future* and 6.3.3, **6.3.3** *Utopias and Imaginaries*.

These themes synthesize various perspectives and insights shared during the expert interviews. However, it is essential to note that this synthesis combines diverse individual opinions into a comprehensive

narrative. As such, some experts emphasized only specific aspects of these themes, which may explain why certain findings do not fully align or integrate seamlessly.

6.3.1 Role of Narratives

The data presented in the two first sub-research questions comes together in this last one, and results are put together to understand the perceived role of counter-hegemonic narratives for the experts interviewed. The analysis set out to explore and understand narratives as a range of sense-making experiences that show the meaning we give the world around us. Therefore, the results were analysed in both a factual and interpretative way. This analysis was carried out to understand how experts perceive the role of narratives and simultaneously look closer at the nature of the diverse narratives they employed while discussing the Yasuni referendum. The previous sub-research questions focused on disassembling certain essential elements of the existing narrative, first looking at the key elements and framings that were part of the counter-hegemonic narratives and then exploring how such narratives envision a post-extractivist transformation.

Narratives were perceived as powerful, especially in triggering imagination, framing possibilities, giving meaning to experiences, and motivating individuals. However, they are also volatile and breakable, need to be constantly sustained, and not enough by themselves to promote change.

Narratives were deemed powerful for several reasons; experts shared their belief that narratives can create a clear vision of the future. As it is in narratives that we recognize what is important to us, some narratives can foster feelings such as solidarity or unity and help vocalize desires, fears, and thoughts. An expert referred to poststructuralism when asked about the role of narratives, explaining that,

“The ideas, the values, and the ethical imaginaries that people have in their heads shape reality much more than just the material realized. So, for me, yes, it is key. In other words, if there are no well-constructed narratives, images, imaginaries that another way of living is possible and really showing that it is possible, there would be no involvement in organizations and their struggle. The thing, the question is, what kind of values and what kind of imaginaries does one create” (E7)

These answers indicate that narratives that trust another world are possible and can be an essential element in fostering social transformations. Correspondingly, it points out a crucial element of the findings: narratives need to be well constructed and have a clear vision to be more powerful. This is further supported by the results in 6.2.2, which summarized what experts deemed necessary for realizing a post-

extractivist transformation, emphasizing the importance of comprehensive long-term planning and increased socio-environmental awareness.

The repeated emphasis on the different levels of awareness in the country highlights its importance for the participants. It could be an essential element to consider while understanding how narratives play a role in a post-extractivist transformation. Awareness was presented as a sign of the world framings present, representing experiences, interests, and understandings of a particular situation and, therefore, an element that shapes how individuals perceive and respond to global issues.

Data analysis also suggested that simple, meaningful narratives can have a powerful impact, as demonstrated by the Yasuni referendum campaign 2023 featuring the slogan *“Yas to Yasuni, yes to life.”* On a similar note, two experts and other data sources focused a considerable amount on how simple and meaningful narratives can awaken feelings of solidarity. It was argued that change in the narrative could happen *“when it moves your head or your heart.”* Suggesting that some elements hold a lot of symbolism and meaning for people; complicated explanations are unnecessary when these elements are included. The simplicity of narratives gains its strength from the lived experiences and belief systems of a person, as shared by an interviewee,

“When I was telling my colleagues, look, this is Yasuní, what impressed them the most was the water. And that was very strong, because, of course, there is no water here [rural coastal region]; there is water there; how can we damage a place where there is water? Like a very simple understanding of what is important in life.” (E3)

Moreover, narratives were perceived as deeply personal, shaped by past experiences and stories we have been told, yet a strong sense of agency was recognized. Most interviewees expressed a desire to assert their voices and ideas rather than unquestionably accepting the truth in everything they have been told. This was often demonstrated in stories of how they became interested in the Yasuni issue, as many experts highly valued their process of constructing their own narrative. Similarly, Indigenous communities seek to regain agency and strength in their narratives by having their voices heard, their stories understood, and their desires realized.

Narratives were characterized to have a volatile and ever-changing nature. Experts acknowledged that narratives change and adapt depending on one's experiences in the present and the past and how one experiences what is happening around them. This was also manifested, for example, when interviewees shared that their motivations changed after having had a personal experience with oil exploitation's impacts or the *Amazonia's* hardships. Likewise, another example was the loss of credibility that the

hegemonic discourse has faced, especially that of the state, as it has been unable to fulfil the promises of development and wealth made more than 50 years ago when oil exploitation began. In this case, a collective narrative gets questioned when lived experiences do not mirror the main narrative used.

Due to this characteristic of continuously changing and changeable narratives, data suggested that narratives must be persistently sustained and reinforced to gain social traction. While a well-established power system sustains hegemonic narratives, counter-hegemonic narratives need to be supported by spaces that create counter-cultures to the mainstream discourse. On the one hand, these spaces are created individually based on one's experiences, framings, and ways of seeing the world; on the other hand, they find space in social groups, where collective narratives are formed. These results also highlight the role of social movements, like YASunidos, in creating and sustaining narratives of societal transformations, stimulating societal debate, and giving continuation to the case over time.

Another reason narratives were perceived as influential in steering social change towards post-extractivist futures was their capacity to give hope and empower individuals. This idea was well explained by an expert, who shared that,

“For probably at least 20 years of my life, I was probably more pessimistic for quite a while. I think now I am maybe gaining a different perspective. An internal desire for optimism is somehow taking over. But for the longest time, I would have said that part of my job as an ecologist and environmental scientist is basically to depress people to the point that they will actually do something about what is going on on the planet. And so, you know, a lot of what I talked about in classes and those kinds of things was basically the statistics of what we are losing, as opposed to the statistics of what we have a chance to save. We still have tremendous opportunities to save things and to save ourselves. But yeah, I think the message of hope and possibilities is a much better one than trying to depress people to the point of desperation” (E5).

Another expert also noted that fatalistic narratives have often dominated environmental discussions yet emphasized that hope persists. Agreeing that *“hope moves more than fear”* draws strength from knowing that past events are positive examples of change and that present actions can influence the future. Because *“where there is action, there is hope.”* In contrast, the fatalistic perspective perpetuates the message that 'all is lost,' discouraging efforts for change and action.

Narratives of hope and action go hand in hand with counter-hegemonic narratives that question the status quo. To explain this point, an expert compared the myth of development to the story *The Emperor's New Clothes* by Hans Christian Andersen in an interview. The story is about an emperor who is obsessed with fine clothing. Two swindlers claim they can make him a magnificent suit of clothes that can only be seen

by intelligent people. The emperor, not wanting to admit he cannot see the clothes, pretends to admire them, as do his courtiers. The news that the emperor has a new suit that only intelligent people can see reaches the whole village; when the emperor parades through the town wearing his "new clothes," everyone pretends to admire. Until a child blurts out the truth: "The Emperor is naked!". The expert explained that the truth is there to be uncovered, but first, one must dare to challenge the main narrative and be different. By telling the right story, one can dismantle structures, uncover interconnections, and change the narrative by creating more awareness. Therefore, one could argue that narratives can reframe what is impossible in the future.

One expert also expressed that when transforming an entire narrative feels overwhelming, it can sometimes be easier to start by identifying what we do not want or our "no-futures," these alternative narratives are just as significant in guiding decisions and shaping perspectives.

Nevertheless, experts also reminded that narratives alone are insufficient on their own to achieve a post-extractivist transformation. This reinforces previous results, such as certain structural elements being challenging to change, the power behind hegemonic narratives, and the difficulties currently faced in Ecuador. In other words,

"the power of language is impressive. What is not enunciated, what is not verbalized, what does not have a solid narrative, does not exist, cannot be contested. Is not enough, of course. But if we look at historical achievements such as inclusive language, gender language, things that may seem very semantic, they have a political background and a fundamental programmatic implication. So yes, narratives are very powerful on the one hand; on the other hand, they are not enough, but they are powerful and necessary." (E6)

Similarly, data suggested that in narrating, we assign meaning to events and experiences through symbolism, motivations, and identities, reinforcing existing belief systems or inspiring new ones. Therefore, past experiences play a crucial role in shaping these narratives.

6.3.2 The Role of the Past and the Present

Elaborating on the previous section, data points out that narratives can be powerful, especially in framing ideas about our possibilities and desires for the future. Tying into the idea that narratives derive their strength from the depth of meaning people assign them prompts the question: *How do narratives gain their meanings?* One element that stood out during the analysis was *the past* and *the present's* role in shaping narratives about the future. Several instances in the data pointed out the meanings assigned to

narratives being rooted in both the past and present, especially on how individuals assign meaning to their lived experiences and storied existence.

On the one hand, *the present* is a moment when we can take action about the future. Therefore, current experiences and knowledge about what is possible influence decisions. Hence, connecting distant desired futures into actions that can be taken here and now helps foster motivation, for instance, by reflecting on the power of democracy or shifting pessimistic narratives into positive, hopeful ones.

Experts also shared their concern about how modern individualistic lifestyles change personal narratives. It was explained that the present can have a cloudy, confusing, fast-paced character, which turns one's focus solely to the here, the now, and the personal interests. This perspective helps to understand previous results, such as why people focus on their benefits and ignore what is happening far away from them as long as they are not impacted.

One expert pointed out that moments such as the Yasuni referendum in 2023 could be opportunities to reinforce one's belief in the possibility of change. The referendum was characterized as "*a moment of reflection for Ecuador,*" emphasizing its potential to shift present dynamics and provoke critical questions about the future. It encouraged a pause in the fast-paced present to decide about the referendum and invited contemplation—specifically regarding the implications of oil exploitation in Ecuador.

On the other hand, *the past* was a topic that shed light on important aspects of narratives. Experts argued that past experiences mainly shape personal identities. In this case, *the past* refers to the past lived by each individual and the past of each person's family and community—the history that happened before one's consciousness. One learns and understands the past through the stories told, so it is also in these narratives about the past that we form a significant part of our identity and beliefs about the world.

Furthermore, when discussing the future of social transformation and the influence of narratives, one expert highlighted that,

"Everybody talks about the future, and nobody sees their own history. That is something very strong for me. And then, all those artefacts, everything that you could really learn to understand yourself better as an Ecuadorian, is there in the Amazon, just like on the coast, by the way. But it is destroyed. And that is another layer that is missing in the discourse. It is not only an issue of extractivism or economics, but it has to do with the search for identity, to study history, to understand better the spaces, themselves and what their genesis is, where they originated, and where they came from. And that is another layer of the issue that I think could be more visible" (E7).

The interviewee further explained that our history shapes our culture and identity. They emphasized that it is essential for people to connect with their own history to foster a sense of identity and strengthen cultural ties, which in turn inspires efforts to preserve it. This theme was prominent in connection to the modern way of life that has become individualistic and disconnected from the past and in explaining the importance of the Amazon for Indigenous worldviews. Places like the Amazon region hold intrinsic value, much of which is rooted in the cultural and symbolic meanings that individuals assign to them. The vision of seeing land and forests as objects that can be commodified without understanding their social, cultural, historical and environmental value was criticised. This is a vision commonly found in oil expansion policies, companies' use of the land, and people who have moved to *Amazonia* to work in the oil industry.

Finally, some interviewees reminded me that social changes deemed unimaginable or unattainable have happened in the past, which is how the past holds proof that change is possible and constantly happening. In this way, the past can be the source of hope and motivation in the present. Provided that we learn from history, we should be careful not to repeat mistakes and recognize patterns that have arisen. Results suggest that the past is the source of several answers and where we base our belief systems. Therefore, it is also in how one understands the past and the present where one can recognize patterns and normalizations of aspects that do not fit one's values- for instance, the normalization of violence and dispossession of Indigenous territories and the concept of sacrificable places and people.

6.3.3 Utopias and Imaginaries

Another prominent topic when discussing narratives' role in a post-extractivist transformation was using *utopias* and *imagining alternative futures*. Participants provided various insights into using utopias or alternative futures in their occupations. Utopias were perceived as a source of guidance, motivation, and hope. The imagination of alternative futures and the search for concretized utopias were also highlighted, significantly to sustain and nurture counter-hegemonic narratives. The different perspectives were put together into four key messages.

First, it was mentioned that utopias can provide a form of guidance. The expert who mentioned this explained that one first has to go through a process of thinking and visualizing their *utopias*. Formulating a utopia can provide insight into the core values one has and provide perspective on “*what really matters.*” Therefore, utopias could be understood as formulating which world one wishes to live in or what would constitute a dystopia.

Second, several experts shared reflections on how events that have happened in the past were once considered utopian, a reminder that motivates the belief that similar radical changes can occur in the future. Indeed, imagining utopian possibilities, however difficult it may be to picture them as possible, was probably a first step towards promoting those radical changes. As one interviewee said,

“In many countries, there is already something like rights of nature, but I want to say that, yes, without these fundamental ideas of utopia, certain organizations and achievements would probably not have been possible, I am quite sure. Those big ideas that another world is possible, where economic gains are not the first thing, but coexistence and quality of life, this is utopia, and sometimes it becomes real. That is one thing, and really getting that [rights of nature, plurinational state, and Buen Vivir] into a constitution, into a state space, that really mobilized a lot, and continues to mobilize many ideas” (E7)

Concretized utopias in groundbreaking events were said to motivate and energize people to keep striving for the change they wanted. Experts described these moments as being charged with energy—energy born from the emergence of new imaginaries based on progressive ideas of the time, such as the conservation of the Yasuni for its intrinsic value.

A third point reflected how the bridge between an imagined utopia and being possible is a well-structured narrative. As mentioned previously, this narrative often supports itself with examples of past “concretized utopias” and is sustained within collective narratives, often in social groups. The need for concrete utopias to support the narrative may help explain why Yasuni’s history has acquired such strong symbolic significance and how it can contribute to a broader transition by symbolizing other possibilities and utopias. Similarly, the use of “Yasunizar” (to yasunize) by YASunidos shows how concrete examples serve the narrative as an example to scale up. When asked what “Yasunizar” meant, an expert said it represented that “*the story goes beyond*” Yasuni, beyond the local case, and stands to show that there are other possibilities for development not only in the Amazonia but also at national and international levels.

Lastly, some experts preferred to use the term *alternative futures* or *imagining alternative futures* rather than utopias. Alternative imaginaries were proposed to be somewhat individual and ever-changing. This volatility makes them prone to loss or sustained depending on the situation in which a person lives. For example, they can be limited by uncertainty and fear; thus, imagining the future could be seen as a privilege that appears when other immediate necessities are covered. As mentioned in the previous question, the current crisis in the country has changed the immediate priorities. In addition, an expert explained that “there are a multiplicity of imaginary futures and that the ways of looking at the future are

infinite,” stressing that there is no one idea of the future but that, as individuals, we can imagine various possibilities.

All in all, alternative imagined futures and utopias play a role in formulating counter-hegemonic narratives and promoting societal transformations. Nevertheless, they must be sustained, especially with proof that they are possible and collective support. There was a reminder of the need for a clear vision, defined values, and a comprehensive medium- and long-term plan to direct change in a specific direction. In formulating these alternative futures, one can decide that *“there is more than what we have been told.”*

7 Discussion of Results

The sub-research questions structured the results and provided a comprehensive understanding of the "macro" counter-hegemonic narratives. The previous section detailed the findings regarding the primary elements of narratives surrounding the Yasuni referendum. It then examined how these narratives envision or address the possibility of a post-extractivist transformation. It concluded by analysing the significance actors attribute to narratives in fostering societal transformations.

This section will draw some conclusions from the findings, guided by the main research question: ***How can counter-hegemonic narratives, as exemplified in the case of the 2023 Yasuni-ITT referendum, contribute to imagining and promoting a post-extractivist transformation?*** The discussion will begin with summarizing the key findings, linking these to relevant concepts from the theoretical framework and literature review. Next, the discussion will focus on six main points. Additionally, the limitations of the findings will be addressed.

The findings reveal that the Yasuni case holds deep symbolic significance in Ecuador, representing alternative possibilities and the defence of life. Framed as a utopia, it challenges dominant views on extractivism, serving as a “*symptom of change*” that unites diverse struggles and social groups while drawing national and international attention for over a decade. Results reinforce the case’s uniqueness and align with Yin’s (2017) rationale for selecting a single case study, making the Yasuni referendum a valuable lens for examining narratives of social transformation. While the debate on Yasuni has broadened national discussions on extractivism, the oil industry’s impacts and resulting social conflicts remain deeply local, particularly affecting Indigenous lifestyles and worldviews. The counter-hegemonic narratives strongly critique the state and oil industry, portraying them as corrupt and indifferent to social and environmental well-being, positioning them as key promoters of the hegemonic narrative—one that, despite its power, has been losing credibility after five decades of oil exploitation. Lastly, the findings acknowledge the structural challenges that limit transformative change, highlighting that while narratives play a crucial role in resistance, they alone may not be sufficient to drive systemic transformation.

The findings of the second sub-research question shed light on how narratives and actors debate the possibility of a post-extractivist transformation while identifying key conditions and aspirations for the future. On an optimistic note, the referendum results were a reason for hope. However, experts also pointed to discouraging factors, such as the state’s financial dependence on extractivism and the persistence of extractive practices beyond the oil sector. The analysis highlighted three crucial elements

for advancing transformation. First, national awareness and dialogue were deemed essential, with experts emphasizing the need for an intercultural and interdisciplinary approach to fostering sustainable societal change. Second, promoting viable alternatives was underscored, as they inspire hope and provide actionable steps for shaping the future. Finally, long-term planning was identified as key to maintaining a clear vision and ensuring progress toward a just and sustainable transition. The aspirations expressed in the findings closely align with theoretical discussions on post-extractivism and post-development, emphasizing the need for a profound transformation that challenges the extractive system at its core (Acosta, 2017; Brand & Wissen, 2012; Gudynas, 2011a).

The analysis of the third sub-research question examined expert responses and narratives surrounding the Yasuni referendum and post-extractivist transitions. Overall, narratives were perceived as powerful tools for triggering imagination, framing possibilities, assigning meaning to experiences, and motivating individuals. However, they are also volatile and dynamic and must be consistently sustained. The data underscored that compelling narratives should be well-constructed yet simple, meaningful, and rich in symbolism. The simplicity of narratives gains strength from a person's lived experiences and belief systems. Optimistic narratives of hope, grounded in past stories and personal experiences, are particularly impactful as they provide agency within broader macro-narratives. Nevertheless, experts cautioned that narratives alone cannot achieve a post-extractivist transformation, highlighting structural challenges, the enduring power of hegemonic narratives, and the difficulties currently faced in Ecuador. The data revealed that the meanings assigned to narratives are deeply rooted in both past experiences and present realities, particularly in how individuals interpret their lived experiences and storied existence. Additionally, utopias and alternative imaginaries emerged as integral components of counter-hegemonic narratives. Utopias were seen as sources of guidance, motivation, and hope, providing a framework for imagining alternative futures.

The findings revealed strong connections to the thesis's main theoretical foci, reinforcing the conceptual framework's relevance. Next, I present how the key themes that shaped the context of this study align with the theories outlined in the theoretical background. This alignment is particularly valuable given that the research was conducted using constructivist grounded theory, meaning the analysis was developed independently of pre-existing academic theories. The fact that the findings coincide with the literature strengthens their credibility, demonstrating that the themes emerging from the data resonate with broader scholarly discussions and validating the study's contributions to the field.

Results showed a resemblance to theories on the significance of narratives on societal transformations. According to Schneider (2019), narratives are fundamental in shaping our understanding of the world and its processes. They are the stories we create to explain the world around us, guiding decisions based on our comprehension of the present and visions for the future (Beckert, 2013; Schneider, 2019). The data collected reflected this, indicating that narratives were expressed as stories representing how individuals and collectives understand the context of the Yasuni referendum. According to Wittmayer et al. (2015), narratives are a discursive form that positions actors within a given context and assigns events or activities in a temporal sequence toward a specific goal or imagined future, which was the case in the data.

Similarly, several findings connect to Gramsci's concept of hegemony (Gramsci, 1992). For instance, the state's role, the oil industry, and the "imperial mode of living" were recognized as key "promoters" of the mainstream narrative. Both the theory of extractivism—particularly the extractive imperative (Arsel et al., 2016a) and commodities consensus (Svampa, 2015)—and references to the hegemonic narrative reflected the TINA principle, as well as the normalization of "common sense" ideas about oil extraction as essential for development (Acosta, 2013; Gramsci, 1992; Schneider et al., 2011). Gudynas (2019) argues that extractive narratives often blend factual assertions with moral premises, interpretations with opinions, and frequently omit or obscure certain information. Experts noted the presence of false or manipulated information disseminated by the state and the marginalization of alternative discourses.

Additionally, Leach et al. (2010) argue that examining how actors and networks produce—and sometimes promote—specific framings is a critical addition to systems perspectives, which otherwise may downplay the agency of certain actors. The results also highlighted the frequent exclusion of Indigenous worldviews and marginalised groups' lack of active participation, demonstrating this dynamic between dominant narratives and alternative perspectives.

The results align well with theories on extractivism, neo-extractivism, and other concepts discussed in the theoretical background, for example, those by Acosta (2013), Gudynas (2019), and Svampa (2015). This is exemplified by the persistence of pro-extractivist discourse regardless of the political administration in power, the connection between extraction and ideas of development, and the focus on extraction for export. Interviewees with academic backgrounds appeared to concur with these theories, recognizing elements of the myth of development and the resource curse (Ross, 1999). Many interviewees emphasized that while the state's discourse on extractivism remains influential, it is losing credibility due to 50 years of unfulfilled promises tied to resource exploitation. The persistence of the state reflects a hegemonic discourse that resists alternative pathways and remains deeply tied to vested interests. This

persistence exemplifies the extractivist mindset of *"to the last drop,"* which was previously presented in the theoretical framework of this thesis (Gudynas, 2019). Simultaneously, the oil industry was held accountable through the explicit naming of companies and was portrayed as a destructive actor solely focused on extraction, disregarding citizen protests and resistance.

While the findings resembled some important aspects of the theoretical background, they also provided interesting insights into the main question that guided the thesis process. In the following part of the discussion, the focus will shift to six main themes and conclusions that directly address the research question, emphasizing the role of counter-hegemonic narratives in fostering post-extractivist transformations.

Problematizing Extractivism for Systemic Change

The first key insight from the data was the emphasis placed by experts and collectives on problematizing and characterizing the current situation. Experts linked the Yasuni referendum to broader systemic issues; a perspective echoed in the documents, which framed interconnected conflicts. This aspect of the diverse narratives analyzed is particularly noteworthy. Despite originating from different actors and viewpoints, the counter-hegemonic narratives converged around problematizing the situation by connecting Yasuni to larger issues. In doing so, these narratives offer an initial glimpse into how transformation is envisioned, beginning with the crucial step of recognizing the core problem. A central theme in these counter-extractivist narratives is the uncovering of systems of oppression, which was evident in the connections to global issues, critiques of structural elements, and the call for systemic and structural change.

In this way, the present narrative provides an initial insight into how a transformation is imagined based on the characterisation of the current problem. The data connected the exploitation of the Yasuni National Park to global unequal exchange, colonial heritage, modes of production, imperial mode of living, and critiques of the development discourse. The state was portrayed as a key proponent of the hegemonic narrative, frequently adhering to discourses rooted in the extractive imperative and commodities consensus, emphasizing the commodification of nature and the designation of sacrificable places.

Additionally, hegemonic interests in extractivism were framed as part of a broader system, encompassing mining and oil industries, sustained by powerful actors and vested interests. Interviewees highlighted the urgent need to fundamentally transform the extractivist model while acknowledging its resilience, adaptability, and entrenched power. Similarly, Gudynas (2011a) argues that post-extractivism is rooted in the question: *"How can we begin to break free from extractivist dependence?"* Rather than calling for a

complete cessation of natural resource extraction, it seeks alternatives to conventional extractivism. Post-extractivism, therefore, represents a rejection of passive acceptance of extractivism and an active effort to explore viable alternatives, an element also prominent in the data collected. This means that successful resistance to promote a post-extractive transition needs to challenge prevailing hegemonic narratives and create their narratives of change, concrete utopias and educated hope.

The Role of Symbolisms

Another important finding was the central role that symbolisms seem to take in counter-hegemonic narratives. The data analysis revealed the significant value and importance of symbols throughout the analysis, such as water, the search for concretized utopias, and the Yasuni, with "*yasunisar*" emerging as a narrative about expanding the Yasuni story to other contexts. The formulation of symbolism appears to be a central element, as experts noted that these symbols reinforce narratives, inspire hope, and serve as a form of concretized utopia. Suggesting that narratives of change gain strength and collective momentum by focusing on clear and meaningful examples, particularly when those examples hold deep significance. This aligns with Levitas' (1990) concept of concrete utopias, which acknowledges the flaws of the present while envisioning achievable pathways toward a more just and equitable society. The findings demonstrate an active pursuit of concretized utopias within the imperfect world, highlighting this process as a key element in generating social change through counter-hegemonic narratives.

The Yasuni case and referendum have gained significant meaning and symbolism in Ecuadorian society. The Yasuni as a symbol was a prominent finding in the results, something that was also supported by literature. Mila Maldonado et al. (2024) highlight that Yasuni has remained a central topic in Ecuadorian media debates. Similarly, Larrea (2024) describes it as a "historic milestone," advocating for the immediate closure of the oil wells. Le Quang (2016) analyses how Yasuni symbolizes alternative possibilities and allows one to explore new imaginaries.

In this context, Yasuni represents a collective struggle, framing climate action as a way of affirming "*yes to life*" and securing a sustainable collective future. My findings and the academic work on Yasuni underscore the importance of the case for the population, particularly demonstrating how it has become representative and symbolic. For example, while the impacts of oil extraction are similar across the Amazon, Yasuni has been a focal point of research and debate due to its megadiversity, the presence of Indigenous peoples in isolation, and the widespread recognition of the importance of the case. Since the Yasuni and its environmental, social, and cultural richness have become known to a broad public, the

destruction of this space has become very symbolic and contested. Nevertheless, the attention to the Yasuni differs from other areas of the Amazon, where oil exploitation has not gained as much attention or national support.

Another symbolic element highlighted in the findings is hope. Levitas (1990) argues that hope is crucial in driving social change, advocating for "educated hope," which combines critical awareness with visionary imagination. The theory of concrete utopias aligns with the results from section 6.2.1, which emphasizes that narratives of hope motivate and empower individuals to participate in change. Similarly, experts shared their sources of hope for a post-extractivist transformation, further exemplifying the centrality of this element in counter-hegemonic narratives. As one expert stated, "*hope moves more than fear*," while another added, "*where there is action, there is hope*."

Narratives and Identities

The findings further emphasize that narratives are deeply intertwined with identities, rooted in understandings of the past and shaped by personal experiences. This connection underscores the multifaceted role of narratives in shaping individual and collective futures and the sense of self and community.

The theoretical background on social transformations highlighted the role of narratives as stories that help us understand the world and guide decisions about the future (Beckert, 2013; Wittmayer et al., 2015). The results align with this perspective and further demonstrate that narratives, stories, and framings are integral to how people construct and share their identities, as claimed in narrative inquiry theory (Bochner & Herrmann, 2020). Narratives, particularly those about the future, reflect our wishes, fears, and needs, revealing how we perceive our position in society, understand our past, and envision the future we desire. They provide a space for discussing present fears and sharing feelings of discouragement or hope. Narratives are not merely the vocalized expression of decision-making processes but also encompass the underlying thoughts, emotions, and experiences that shape these processes.

One notable element connected to identities is the dominance of Western-modern lifestyles, which emphasize individuality and monetary growth while promoting detachment from personal histories. The results suggest that modernity plays a central role in the hegemonic narrative. This narrative of detachment from history appears to align with hegemonic interests, potentially reinforcing arguments favouring oil exploitation and feelings of helplessness in isolated resistance. These results are similar to the imperial mode of living, a dominant way of life rooted in capitalist production and consumption

patterns tied to ideas and narratives of progress, often disregarding social and ecological consequences (Brand & Wissen, 2012).

Another important aspect is the loss of historical and cultural value that occurs as collateral damage from oil exploitation. This loss makes it difficult for individuals to maintain their sense of identity, and in the case of oral traditions, Indigenous sites, or artefacts, such cultural elements may be lost forever. Mirroring Svampa's *eco-territorial turn* concept on how contemporary struggles in Latin America center on land and territories and are linked to fights for autonomy, self-determination, environmental protection, and resistance against social marginalization (Svampa, 2015).

This identity element reflects a broader impact of the extractive industry in many ways: the past shapes how we construct our identities and envision our future. When the connection to the past is cut, belief systems are thrown into doubt. This impact can be especially difficult for communities whose worldview and culture are deeply intertwined with the surrounding Nature and Land. Soliz Torres et al. (2023, p. 153) highlight the impact on body-territory through illness, pointing out that *“the body is the territory in which the processes of health-disease live, traversed by culture and the historical-political moment in which it finds itself.”* In this body-territory, the suffering and effects of oil extractivism are embodied, as well as environmental pollution and its associated consequences. At the local level, extractivism has a *“psycho-affective and psycho-social dimension of cultural rootlessness and the self”* (Soliz Torres et al., 2023, p. 153, own translation).

Thus, the extractivist model significantly impacts the loss of cultural identity and connection to land. At local and national levels, elements were identified where this was important. On the one hand, the imperial mode of living creates identities disconnected from the past and focuses on monetary status and the future. On the other hand, communities rooted in their territory lose cultural value along with the loss of their land.

Co-Creating the Future by Looking at the Past

The fourth key finding highlights the role of narratives of the past in shaping alternative futures. This finding closely connects to the previous discussion on the connection of narratives to identities, emphasizing the significance of history and the "walked path" in co-creating a desired future. Notably, while this thesis has a future-oriented focus of analysis, the findings reveal that envisioning the future is more deeply intertwined with the past than one might initially assume.

Findings often focused on how people discuss the present and the past, basing decision-making on their understanding of the world, themselves, and their position and agency. Personal identities based on our understanding of one's history become a protagonist's role in framing desires for the future and actions of the present. Bochner et al. (2020, p. 287) explain that *"as students and family members, we read, write, and/or listen to stories, learning to compare and analyse them. The stories we are exposed tell us who we are, where we are located in ethnic, family, racial, sexual, and cultural history; where we have come from; where we may be going; what we can say and do; and with whom. Passed to us by our elders and significant others, these stories become our narrative inheritance"*. In the concept of *"living through our storied existence,"* the results of this thesis can gain much insight.

As presented in section 6.3.2 on the past and present, many narratives of change are connected to our perceptions of both. One expert emphasized the importance of learning from the past to create a sustainable and just future. The system of extractivism and territorial struggles gains strength by disconnecting individuals from their historical-cultural values, especially if they are interested in using those lands. So, by connecting narratives to lived history, experienced conflicts and the culture of ancestors, a counter-extractivist culture is created that values the intrinsic value of the territory.

Similarly, hegemonic narratives invoke the TINA principle, committing to the idea that there are no other options. Nevertheless, findings demonstrate several positive examples from the past that were deemed impossible at the time. Therefore, looking at the past can also be a source of hope.

Reflecting on the past allows for critically examining the elements that history has normalized but can be questioned. Hegemonic narratives shape dominant pathways and establish "common senses," often obscuring their historical construction. By analyzing the past, there is an opportunity to uncover how these pathways emerged and to identify which aspects of modern society are currently being normalized or stem from revolutionary ideas. For instance, understanding the history of colonization enables Indigenous communities to challenge the normalization of their marginalization and struggle. Similarly, modern societies' fast-paced, resource-intensive lifestyles are not inevitable but the product of historical processes that have become unquestioned norms. Recognizing these patterns creates space for reimagining alternatives and fostering transformative change. Breaking the narratives of individualism, disinterest in the common good, and lack of confidence in change are the keys to co-creating futures built on solidarity, collaboration, and sustainability.

The Possibility of Change and Imaginary Utopias

A key finding from the analysis is that counter-hegemonic narratives are crucial in communicating the possibility of change and co-creating desired futures. Experts frequently emphasized the need to break mental barriers and reinforce that transforming current pathways is achievable. These narratives are constructed through various elements—historical understandings, system critiques, and symbolism—all of which expand the boundaries of imagination and legitimize the pursuit of alternative futures. These narratives highlight the tangible nature of utopian aspirations by focusing on hope, action, agency, and the intrinsic value of meaningful yet simple aspects of life. Moreover, rather than purely visionary, the narratives analyzed were well-supported by concrete proposals, factual explanations, and clear connections, reinforcing their credibility and transformative potential.

While acknowledging the structural and systemic elements of extractivism—thereby highlighting a limitation of narratives alone—there were also expressions of hope for transformation and reflections on what such change might entail. For instance, it was emphasized that it is essential to focus on what can be done here and now, reinforcing theories of social transformation that argue that current narratives shape our future by influencing decision-making processes (Beckert, 2013) narratives as *politics of signification* (Wittmayer et al., 2015), and theories on prefigurative politics that call to embody “the change you want to see” (Jeffrey & Dyson, 2021). Similarly, the results from sub-research question II in section 6.2 showed reasons to maintain hope, including narratives of hope and action, promoting intercultural and multidisciplinary dialogue, and increased socio-environmental awareness.

The findings also emphasized that envisioning transformation requires long-term planning and visualizing alternatives. This process helps open imaginaries, turning abstract desires into tangible forms, which can guide transformation in the desired direction while motivating and empowering individuals. Such elements were crucial for the counter-hegemonic narratives to be credible and collectively reproduced.

Among the desires for the future, the Yasuni case was recognized as a focal point for broader discussions on transformation. Some experts shared visions extending beyond reforming the oil extraction industry, encompassing the redistribution of wealth, fostering self-sufficiency, incorporating alternative worldviews, and promoting direct democracy, among others. These elements align closely with the theories presented in the section 4.1.2. For example, it ties in with the discussion presented by Acosta and Brand (2018), who argue that post-extractivism and de-growth are interconnected transformations. Elements of *Buen Vivir* and *epistemologies of the South* were also found in how actors question Western

narratives that ignore different ways of organizing life and the economy (Acosta, 2017; Sousa Santos, 2011). These elements reinforce the finding that counter-hegemonic narratives often foster alternative viewpoints to uncover more possibilities for the future.

Promoting Counter-Hegemonic Narratives

When examining the role of narratives in fostering societal transformations, it is essential to consider how they are promoted, sustained, and can gain influence—especially when they lack the structural support of hegemonic narratives. According to Wittmayer (2015), narratives must be actively promoted and believed to create impact. While counter-hegemonic narratives play a crucial role in challenging dominant systems, their primary limitation lies in their volatility and susceptibility to dissipate if not continuously reinforced. Counter-extractive narratives face opposition from mainstream narratives that are institutionalized and embedded in daily life and infrastructure, making any transformation a long-term process. For these narratives to have lasting influence, they must be sustained over time alongside a persistent social desire for change.

The findings highlight several factors that can promote these narratives. Key elements identified include the need for moments of reflection, lived experiences, and hope, alongside the role of social groups that actively reproduce counter-hegemonic narratives. Changing dominant narratives requires opportunities for reflection, compelling arguments, and personal experiences that challenge "common sense" assumptions.

Collective narratives that promote hope, solidarity and cooperation were identified as especially effective in fostering change. This was complemented by the belief that increased social and environmental awareness might promote counter-extractivist narratives. The results also reveal that social-environmental awareness varies among different social groups, suggesting that Yasuni exemplifies not only an environmental struggle but also a social class one. Lived experiences of vulnerability and state neglect serve as the foundation for powerful narratives, highlighting the significance of symbols in representing and conveying these realities. Furthermore, the findings indicate that narratives are shaped not only by social class but also by personal experiences and values.

An important finding is social movements' role as counter-hegemonic narrative promoters. Established groups, including those involved in the Yasuni campaign, have contributed to the creation of critical narratives that challenge the extractive model while also questioning dominant modes of production, conventional ideas of development, and patterns of unequal exchange. The findings also highlight

YASunidos' role in sustaining the Yasuni debate and struggle over the years. As a key promoter of critical, counter-hegemonic narratives, the collective has institutionalized and actively advanced this perspective. Mancilla and Martínez (2014) further document the movement's impact on shaping the national debate.

7.1 Limitations and Considerations for Interpretation

While the results provide valuable insights, it is important to acknowledge limitations that could influence their interpretation. Methodological limitations, such as those presented in 3.5, must be considered, along with recognized limitations in the analysis and generalization of findings.

In this thesis, multiple sources of evidence were used for triangulation, providing an opportunity to develop converging lines of inquiry and conduct an in-depth study of the phenomenon within its real-world context, which was crucial for this research. However, given the individual nature of narratives, achieving (and even defining) a saturation point is challenging. This difficulty is further compounded by the high dynamism and multiplicity of narratives, adding an element of subjectivity to the analysis shaped by the individuals interviewed and the specific time frame in which the interviews occurred. Although the study involved a diverse group of experts, this subjectivity represents a limitation that must be acknowledged. Additionally, while it was impossible to generalize all aspects of the narratives, the focus was placed on identifying robust and prominent themes rather than specific personal opinions.

This thesis argues that Yasuni represents a valuable case for investigating counter-hegemonic narratives. While the Yasuni case proved to be unique and highly significant, making it well-suited for this research, it is important to emphasize that it does not necessarily reflect the local realities of the entire Amazon region. Other areas of the *Amazonia* affected by exploitation have not received the same national and international support. Yasuni remains a unique case due to its history and the ITT Initiative, which introduced a paradigm shift and provided an exceptional opportunity to analyse narratives of change. Nevertheless, caution must be exercised in generalizing these results to the broader Amazonian context.

Moreover, no universally agreed-upon definition of post-extractivist transformation was found. While various theoretical discussions were presented, this thesis recognizes that there are multiple ways of envisioning such a transformation; defining this was not the primary focus of the study. This diversity was also reflected in the data, where responses about transformation varied significantly. This limitation is both a relevant result and a point of caution. On the one hand, the openness in defining post-extractivism transformation allows for a wide range of narratives and imaginaries to be present. On the other hand, it introduces a degree of subjectivity into the analysis and interpretation, making it difficult at times to

discern whether the discussion pertains to general social transformation or, specifically, post-extractivism. Post-extractivism is embedded in theoretical debates about global and local production systems, so narratives about these systems were also considered part of post-extractivist discourse.

Overall, this study provided valuable insights into the role of narratives in promoting a post-extractivist transformation. The findings were connected to key theoretical frameworks through thorough analysis and discussion, reinforcing their validity. Six main themes were examined in more detail in response to the research question, highlighting critical aspects of counter-hegemonic narratives.

8 Conclusion

This thesis set out to understand narratives of hope, resistance, and transformation in the face of extractive hegemony. Through analysis and thoughtful engagement with theory and practice, this thesis seeks to contribute to ongoing discussions on the possibilities for a just, equitable, and sustainable future. This study examined how counter-hegemonic narratives, exemplified in the Ecuadorian referendum banning oil exploitation in the ITT block in the Yasuni National Park in August 2023, contribute to imagining and promoting post-extractivist transformations. Drawing on the methodological framework of case study research outlined by Yin (2017), this study analyses the narratives that emerged during the Yasuni referendum campaign and from some experts involved.

This thesis collected data from four sources, the principal being expert interviews with actors involved in the Yasuni referendum. Results were structured around the three sub-research questions and later discussed, connecting to other theories and academic literature. While the theoretical background proved fit for analysing the topic, the constructivist grounded theory approach was essential to avoid biases in data analysis and collection and to remain open to results. The case study chosen fit adequately with the research at hand; the long history of the Yasuni provided rich insights, and the national nature of the Yasuni referendum offered an ideal moment for narrative analysis of extractivism. The referendum was a good point to fix the attention on one element of an otherwise extensive case and proved to be a topic of national debate in the country. Similarly, a counter-hegemonic nature was recognised in narratives promoting the Yasuni National Park conservation.

The results broadly align with theories on extractivism, post-extractivism, and narratives in societal transformations. While no academic literature was found to have the same focus or methodologies, the literature review provided essential groundwork and insights into the Yasuni case. These insights complemented the findings of this thesis analysis. Therefore, the results of this thesis offer a unique perspective on counter-hegemonic narratives and their role in post-extractivist transformations, filling a gap in the existing academic literature and building on prior research.

To address the central question: **How can counter-hegemonic narratives, as exemplified in the case of the 2023 Yasuni-ITT referendum, contribute to imagining and promoting a post-extractivist transformation?** Here are some conclusions.

First, a key element is that it is through narrating that the framing of the world, its problems, and potential solutions crystallize. The framing employed often reflects the observations and perceptions of specific actors, giving voice to their feelings and experiences regarding a particular situation. For example, in the case of the Yasuni, these narratives focused on illustrating the issue's complexities, emphasizing its embeddedness within modes of production. In this way, framings help narratives characterize the world, providing a lens through which people can understand both the present and the past.

A second conclusion is that symbolism plays a central role in counter-hegemonic narratives, reinforcing messages of resistance, hope, and transformation. The findings highlight the significance of symbols such as water, concretized utopias, and the Yasuni itself in strengthening narratives and inspiring collective action. For instance, a key symbolic element is hope; the data reflected this through narratives emphasizing action-driven hope as a catalyst for transformation. Ultimately, the role of symbolism in counter-hegemonic narratives highlights the power of meaningful representation in shaping collective imaginaries and fostering social transformation.

A third significant role of narratives was their capacity to build identities. Through our storied existence, we learn who we are and what is important to us. Narratives derive meaning from the past and present, shaping how individuals assign significance to their lived experiences. Stories about the past construct our understanding of the present and influence how we perceive our position within it. This process, in turn, plays a crucial role in imagining possibilities and aspirations for the future. The connection between narratives and personal or collective identity emerged across various themes, demonstrating its importance when analysing narratives related to post-extractivist transformations. In this issue, the territorial scope is quite relevant as it is strongly connected to Indigenous cosmovisions, which have gone through processes of colonisation and dispossession of their territories.

In connection with this, the fourth conclusion underscores the crucial role of narratives of the past in shaping alternative futures, revealing that future-oriented thinking is deeply intertwined with historical consciousness. Personal and collective histories shape identities and influence present actions and future aspirations. Reflecting on the past also exposes how hegemonic narratives have normalized dominant pathways, allowing for a critical reassessment of what modern society takes for granted.

Fifth, counter-hegemonic narratives play a vital role in communicating the possibility of change. Experts stressed the need to break mental barriers and legitimize alternative pathways through historical perspectives, system critiques, and symbolism. These narratives emphasize hope, action, and agency,

making utopian aspirations feel tangible. Utopias and alternative Imaginaries became vital elements of counter-hegemonic narratives, serving as sources of inspiration, guidance, and hope by offering frameworks for envisioning alternative futures.

Lastly, the promotion and sustainability of counter-hegemonic narratives are essential for fostering societal transformation, particularly when these narratives lack structural support. While they challenge dominant systems, their impact depends on continuous reinforcement and collective belief. The findings highlight key factors that support these narratives, including moments of reflection, lived experiences, and social movements that cultivate awareness and solidarity. Social groups emerged as the primary promoters of critical post-extractivist narratives, playing a vital role in sustaining and nurturing the debate and bringing it to public awareness. Similarly, the importance of raising social and environmental awareness and fostering intercultural and multidisciplinary dialogue was highlighted.

Counter-hegemonic narratives face several limitations that challenge their transformative potential. Experts emphasize that systemic change is slow due to entrenched structures like the global order, colonial legacies, IMF contracts, and social inequality, all reinforced by powerful actors. Additionally, these narratives struggle to gain traction in a fast-paced world dominated by individualism and resource-intensive lifestyles. Their success depends on being actively promoted, heard, and believed. Lastly, narratives are dynamic and shaped by personal experiences, making them adaptable and fragile—while some endure, others shift or fade, often influenced by crises or evolving perspectives.

In conclusion, alternative narratives play a crucial role in imagining different futures, giving meaning to experiences, and empowering individuals. They help construct ideals, recognize values and needs, and trigger imagination, serving as a means of concretizing new possibilities. As demonstrated by YASunidos, narratives of change must be actively promoted to become collective forces for transformation. While the Yasuni case represents significant progress, it remains a small-scale victory within a broader counter-hegemonic struggle. The referendum's success reflects a societal desire for sustainable development, signalling a shift rather than a complete transformation—a *"symptom of change."* Notably, we cannot create what we cannot imagine; narratives may not change the world independently, but this research highlights their essential role in fostering transformation. Societal change is ongoing despite hegemonic forces pushing the idea of a single, unchangeable path. Counter-hegemonic narratives challenge this notion, proving that multiple futures are possible and that individuals have the power to participate in shaping them.

8.1.1 Recommendations for Further Research

While the methods employed in this research were well-suited to achieving its aims, incorporating ethnographic methods in future studies could provide a deeper understanding of narratives. Ethnographic approaches involving immersive and detailed community engagement could uncover how narratives are experienced, shared, and transformed within specific contexts. An ethnographic methodology would enhance the richness of insights into the dynamics of counter-hegemonic narratives and their role in societal transformations.

The research highlighted the significant role of narratives in fostering climate and social awareness. However, further investigation is needed to identify which specific narratives or discourses are most effective in achieving this goal. This study identified optimistic and symbolic narratives as particularly impactful, but future research could explore these and other narrative forms in greater detail. Such studies could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the stories and messaging strategies that resonate with different audiences and drive awareness and action.

One conclusion is that while narratives are powerful, other factors must complement them to drive societal transformation effectively. Comprehensively identifying these additional factors was beyond the scope of this study but would serve as an intriguing focus for future research.

Finally, while this thesis engaged with a selection of theories on societal transformations and narratives, numerous other theoretical frameworks were not included. Further theoretical research that systematically compares, contrasts, and unifies these theories would be highly valuable. Such work could contribute to developing a more cohesive theoretical foundation for understanding the relationship between narratives and societal transformations, paving the way for robust interdisciplinary research in the future.

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